

D5.1: Trust Orchestrator (first version)

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the first integrated version of the Trust Orchestrator Framework. As part of WP5, it integrates key security assessment technologies from WP3 (Static & Dynamic Analysis) and trust enforcement mechanisms from WP4 into a coherent solution, the "RESCALE Platform".

The document outlines the architecture, functionalities, and initial deployment of the framework, focusing on the interaction between its core domains: Assessment, Security & Trust, and Management. Key integration components such as the State Manager, Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR), along with the security validation data flows are described in detail. Additionally, this deliverable discusses the continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) approach, the use of containerized environments, the challenges encountered and the technical infrastructure supporting the platform.

By establishing a foundational, trusted supply-chain prototype, this version of the Trust Orchestrator Framework sets the stage for further refinements, validation, and deployments in subsequent project phases.

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List of Abbreviations

- ABI** Application Binary Interface. 33
- API** Application Programming Interface. 5, 11, 16, 17, 22, 24, 26, 29, 30, 36, 37, 41, 45, 54–56
- BOM** Bill of Materials. 10
- BOV** Bill Of Vulnerabilities. 42–44, 65
- CI/CD** Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment. 5, 9, 45, 46, 48, 50–55, 57–59, 61, 62, 65, 66
- CVE** Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures. 15, 28, 32
- CWE** Common Weakness Enumeration. 15
- DevOps** Development Operations. 51, 53
- DL** Deep Learning. 15
- DLT** Distributed Ledger Technology. 32
- DSCG** Dynamic Supply Chain component Guarantee. 9, 15–18, 21, 23, 24, 27, 29–31, 37, 40, 42, 43, 60, 65
- HTTPS** Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure. 62
- IAM** Identity & Access Management. 17, 25, 49, 50, 60
- JSON** JavaScript Object Notation. 36, 43, 55
- JWT** JSON Web Token. 23, 25
- LDAP** Lightweight Directory Access Protocol. 48, 49
- MFA** Multi-Factor Authentication. 50
- ML** Machine Learning. 15
- OIDC** OpenID Connect. 48, 50, 59
- RBAC** Role-Based Access Control. 48–50, 53
- REST** Representational State Transfer. 11, 16
- SAML** Security Assertion Markup Language. 49
- SBOM** Software Bill of Materials. 5, 9, 14–16, 23, 27–31, 35, 37–40, 42–44, 60, 65

SCM Source Code Management. 46

SSCG Static Supply Chain component Guarantee. 9, 15–18, 21, 23, 24, 27, 29–31, 37–43, 60, 65

SSL Secure Sockets Layer. 62

SSO Single Sign-On. 49, 50

TBOM Trusted Bill of Materials. 8, 9, 11, 15–18, 24, 27, 28, 30, 32–34, 42–44, 60, 65

TLS Transport Layer Security. 62

TrustOR Trust Orchestrator Component. 1, 5, 8, 9, 11, 13, 16, 22, 24, 28, 29, 31, 32, 38–40, 42–44, 52, 53, 57, 60

UUID Universally Unique Identifier. 28

VCS Version Control System. 46

VM Virtual Machine. 5, 47, 48, 54, 56, 58–62

WP Work Package. 9, 66

1 Introduction

This deliverable presents the first integrated version of the Trust Orchestrator Framework, which forms the foundation of the RESCALE project. The framework integrates multiple security and trust-related components with the goal of providing a platform that ensures trust in the software supply chain. The following sections outline its purpose, contributions, and alignment with the project's objectives. This work is carried out as part of WP5, specifically under Task 5.1, which focuses on the integration and deployment of RESCALE solutions.

1.1 Scope & Contribution

The Trust Orchestrator Framework is the overarching system within RESCALE that integrates all security and trust-related components developed by project partners. It integrates multiple tools and technologies that collectively ensure supply chain security, enable validation and enforce trust.

The operations of the Static Analysis and Dynamic Testing tools were previously described in WP3 deliverables, submitted in November 2024, and cover with details how the 1st domain of the RESCALE architecture works, specifically the:

- **The Assessment Domain**, responsible for combining multiple and different ways of testing software and hardware.

With this deliverable, D5.1, our focus now shifts to the other two key domains of the RESCALE architecture :

- **The Management Domain**, responsible for orchestrating and integrating security assessment components.
- **The Security & Trust Domain**, which ensures the trustworthiness of security validation and assurance mechanisms.

In particular, WP3 tools interact with the Trust Orchestrator Framework by generating security analysis results that are submitted to the Management Domain and specifically the State Manager component. State Manager acts as an intermediary, it's the entry-point for receiving static and dynamic analysis results, which are then forwarded and processed by other components of the framework. This document focuses on two critical components: the State Manager and the TrustOR component (TrustOR). These components form the backbone of RESCALE's security validation and trust establishment processes.

The State Manager is a key component of the framework, serving as the central coordination point for user interactions and security data management. The Dashboard relies on the State Manager as its backend service, providing end-users with visibility into security assessments. Tools from the Assessment Domain submit their results to the State Manager. The State Manager, however, depends on TrustOR for handling all Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM)-related processes.

The Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR) component is responsible for validating, consolidating, and structuring the SBOMs, SSCGs, and DSCGs that flow through the State Manager from the WP3 tools. It ensures that all security assessment outputs are properly validated before they are integrated into the TBOM. TrustOR also plays a critical role in combining multiple security inputs to generate trusted artifacts, making it a key enabler of the RESCALE security model.

Deliverable **D5.1 - Trust Orchestrator (first version)**, describes the first integrated version of the Trust Orchestrator Framework and outlines:

- The architecture of the Trust Orchestrator Framework, covering its three domains (Assessment, Security & Trust, and Management) and the interplay between their respective components.
- The role of the State Manager as a central hub for user interactions and security data management and its dependency on TrustOR for TBOM-related processes.
- The function of TrustOR as the TBOM validation and generation engine, responsible for consolidating and structuring security assessment results.
- The integration of partner-developed components, including assessment tools, security repositories, state management, and the dashboard.
- The deployment and validation activities, detailing the CI/CD approach, containerized infrastructure, and automated workflows used for platform integration.
- The challenges and next steps, including ongoing efforts to enhance security, refine trust models, and optimize platform deployment for future iterations.

This version of the framework establishes the fundamental integration mechanisms and serves as a foundation for future refinements, ensuring that RESCALE's security and trust mechanisms continue to evolve.

1.2 Relation to Work Packages, Deliverables, and Activities

This deliverable is part of Work Package 5 (WP5) - Integration, Deployment, and Validation, which is responsible for:

- Integrating technologies from WP3 (Static and Dynamic Analysis) and WP4 (Trusted Supply Chain Establishment) into a unified framework.
- Deploying the Trust Orchestrator Framework in pilot environments.
- Validating and evaluating the effectiveness of the integrated solution.

This deliverable primarily takes input from WP3 and WP4 and consolidates their outcomes into a single integrated framework. Specifically:

- The outputs of WP3 are integrated into the Trust Orchestrator Framework to ensure software components undergo rigorous security validation and results are given as input to the platform.
- The outputs of WP4, such as Bill of Materials (BOM) file specifications and mechanisms for trusted supply chain assurance, blockchain-based security validation, and policy enforcement, are incorporated into the framework to establish end-to-end trust in the software supply chain.

Furthermore, D5.1 serves as an input for future WP5 deliverables, including those related to deployment, testing, and validation (e.g., D5.3 - Pilot Deployment, Test, and Demonstration). The integration activities described in this document provide the technical foundation for further validation efforts and real-world testing in RESCALE's pilot environments.

1.2.1 Connections to Other Deliverables

This deliverable is closely connected to several other deliverables within the RESCALE project, either by taking input from them or providing output to later stages of the integration and validation process. More specifically:

- **D4.1 - Specification of the TBOM Structure:** Provides the *data model for TBOMs*, which TrustOR implements and uses to manage security validation.
- **D4.2 - RESCALE Continuous Security Assurance Platform:** Defines the *continuous security monitoring mechanisms*, which TrustOR integrates into its validation workflows.
- **D5.3 - Pilot Deployment, Test and Demonstration (first version):** Describes the *deployment and initial testing* of the Trust Orchestrator Framework. D5.1 establishes the technical foundation for these activities.
- **D5.5 - Validation and Evaluation Report (first version):** Documents the *evaluation of the first integration cycle*, including pilot deployments and testing results of the prototype version of all components. The integration work described in D5.1 serves as the basis for this validation process.

The Trust Orchestrator Framework serves as the convergence point for all security-related processes, ensuring that different components work together seamlessly. By integrating security validation mechanisms from WP3 and WP4, this framework enables structured assessment, trust enforcement, and automation of security policies within RESCALE.

1.3 Contribution to WP5 and Project Objectives

Deliverable D5.1 aligns with WP5 Objective O5.1, as it describes the first integration of WP3, WP4 and WP5 technologies into a unified, secure-by-design supply-chain framework. This deliverable lays the foundation for O5.2, ensuring that the integrated solution is ready for future

deployment into use case environments as specified in Task 2.1. Additionally, the integration activities in D5.1 contribute to O5.3 and O5.4, as they establish the technological basis that will be further tested, demonstrated, and validated in later project phases. Specifically:

- D5.1 directly supports O5.1, as it describes the first integrated version of the Trust Orchestrator Framework, which unifies the security assessment tools developed in WP3 (Static Analysis & Dynamic Testing), the design and specifications defined in WP4 (Trusted Supply Chain Establishment) and the WP5 components which support the actual integration and management of every RESCALE component.
- D5.1 lays the foundation for O5.2, as it defines the first implementation of the Trust Orchestrator Framework, which will later be deployed into real-world use cases in Task 2.1. The deliverable establishes the core functionalities, which will be expanded and tested in the deployment phase of Task 5.2.
- D5.1 sets up the foundation for future testing to be covered in Task 5.3 and deliverable D5.5. The integration work described in D5.1 ensures that the Trust Orchestrator Framework is functional and ready for subsequent validation in real-world applications.
- D5.1 contributes to O5.4 by defining the initial integrated solution and ensuring that its design aligns with RESCALE’s security and trust requirements. It outlines the components, security mechanisms, and validation methods that will be used in future evaluation phases.

Objective	Description
O5.1	Integration of different technologies developed within WP3 and WP4 into a coherent framework (TrustOR).
O5.2	Deploy integrated solutions into the actual use case environments as specified in Task 2.1 and implement the pilot applications.
O5.3	Test and demonstrate the real-world applications that use RESCALE solutions.
O5.4	Validate implemented solutions against requirements and evaluate results against ambitions and targets.

Table 1: WP5 Objectives

1.4 Structure of the Document

This document is organized as follows:

- **Chapter 2 - Trust Orchestrator Framework:** Explains the architecture of the Trust Orchestrator Framework, detailing the role of TrustOR and its interactions with other components.
- **Chapter 3 - Trust Orchestrator Framework Functionalities:** Provides an in-depth view of TrustOR’s REST API, security validation flows, and its management of TBOMs.

- **Chapter 4 - Integration Activities:** Describes the technologies and deployment processes used to connect and validate the different components.
- **Chapter 5 - Conclusions & Future Steps:** Summarizes key findings, discusses integration challenges, and outlines next steps for future iterations.

This deliverable serves as a technical reference for project partners and stakeholders, detailing how RESCALE components within the Trust Orchestrator Framework work together to enable secure and validated software supply chains.

2 Trust Orchestrator Framework

The Trust Orchestrator Framework in RESCALE is a modular, multi-domain system that integrates various security, assessment and management components to establish a secure and trustworthy software supply chain. A fully detailed description of the framework was initially introduced in **Deliverable D2.5: High-Level Architecture (first version)**, which outlined its architectural domains, components, and their interactions.

This chapter provides a concise summary of these domains and their key components to ensure essential context for the reader. This background knowledge is necessary to understand the functionality and role of the Trust Orchestrator Framework within RESCALE.

To complement the textual descriptions, we also provide Figure 1, which presents the high-level architecture diagram from D2.5. This visual representation serves as a reference point, helping the reader navigate the architectural structure and understand how the different components are interconnected.

- **Assessment Domain:** Responsible for analyzing the security and compliance of software and hardware components using Static Code Analysis and Dynamic Testing.
- **Management Domain:** Handles the integration, coordination, and governance of all framework components, including State Manager, Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR), Dashboard, Authentication, and Communication Mechanisms.
- **Security & Trust Domain:** Ensures the trustworthiness of supply chain components through mechanisms such as security assurance, repositories, and ledger-based trust storage.

Each of these domains plays a crucial role in managing, enforcing and validating security policies within the RESCALE ecosystem.

Figure 1: RESCALE High-level Architecture depicting the 3 domains

2.1 Assessment Domain

The Assessment Domain relates to the modules for evaluating software code through static and dynamic testing techniques. Static testing analyzes the code without executing it, detecting potential issues such as syntax errors, security vulnerabilities, and code quality violations. This process helps developers identify defects early, reducing debugging costs and improving maintainability. Dynamic testing, on the other hand, involves executing the code in a controlled environment to evaluate its runtime behavior. This approach helps uncover issues related to performance, memory usage, concurrency, and security threats that might not be evident in static analysis.

The following components within the RESCALE integrated solution contribute to both static and dynamic evaluation, ensuring a comprehensive approach to software assessment:

- **Static Code Analysis Module** - Processes software projects, specifically their source code and the SBOM associated with it, to identify and assess potential security vulnera-

bilities and weaknesses. It employs advanced ML and DL enhanced static code analyzers, which go beyond traditional methods to detect issues more effectively. This module currently incorporates several tools (SASter-cli, SAVE-ME, the intelligent vulnerabilities exposure engine, RefactorERL, DetectEr) to deliver security insights across multiple programming languages. The outcome of this module is the SSCG, a detailed report that includes the types of tests performed, their results, the identity of the evaluator, the version of the assessed asset etc. The SSCG is generated using a newly developed piece of software, the SSCG Generator, and it can be published to the management domain for further processing or just stored locally for inspection without exposing information to the public. More information about this module is available in D3.1.

- **Dynamic Testing Module** - Identifies vulnerabilities across hardware, firmware, and software in the supply chain, employing various dynamic testing techniques for each component. This module includes a Low-level System Components Assessment to detect microarchitectural and OS vulnerabilities, a Dynamic Hardware Analyzer to identify software and hardware vulnerabilities on hardware type of attacks (e.g., Side Channel Attacks), and a Dynamic Software Testing component that uses ML/DL enhanced fuzzing tools for black-box and gray-box testing. Once the dynamic testing analysis is complete, the results from the tools together with the SSCG from static code analysis are forwarded to the DSCG Generator, which compiles these findings into the DSCG. This DSCG serves as a security validation for the runtime aspects of the software, ensuring that vulnerabilities detected during dynamic testing are properly documented and addressed. Each component of the Dynamic Testing module is documented across multiple deliverables and more details can be found in deliverables D3.3, D3.5 and D3.7.

Both static and dynamic testing strive to utilize guidelines like Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE) and Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) to report identified weaknesses and vulnerabilities in a standardized way.

2.2 Security & Trust Domain

The security and trust domain encompasses end-to-end trust establishment for the RESCALE platform across all aspects of the system; from the point an SBOM and SSCG is ingested into the platform, up to the point of a TBOM being generated and validated. The security and trust domain includes continuous vulnerability detection and security assurance using the Security Assurance component, trusted storage using a Hyperledger Besu blockchain, and generic identity and integrity mechanisms such as the use of hashing and digital signatures across the platform. However, this final item will not be included in the first version of the Trust Orchestrator.

- **Bill of Materials Security and Trust Mechanism:** The Bill of Materials Security and Trust Mechanism's guarantee of trust is rooted in an immutable ledger. Beyond this, cryptographic mechanisms such as hashing and signatures used at each stage of the TBOM generation process will provide the baseline inputs to verifiably provide trust that a TBOM is authentic and has not been tampered with.
- **Continuous Security Assurance:** The RESCALE Continuous Security Assurance is split into two elements. The first of these is focused on the security of the RESCALE

platform and entails placing event captors throughout the platform to detect malicious ongoing. The second element is the continuous vulnerability detection which informs of when new vulnerabilities are found for a target present software or dependency present in a TBOM on the RESCALE platform.

2.3 Management Domain

The Management Domain is responsible for orchestrating and coordinating all components within the Trust Orchestrator Framework. It ensures that the various security and assessment mechanisms are integrated efficiently, enabling seamless communication between the security analysis tools, the validation mechanisms, and the trust enforcement processes. To achieve this, it encompasses several key functions, including:

- Lifecycle management of security assessments and trust models
- Interoperability between RESCALE components
- User interaction, visualization, and control mechanisms

The core components of this domain are the State Manager, the Trust Orchestrator component (TrustOR), the Dashboard, and the Authentication / Identity Access Management mechanism. These components are explained in more detail below.

- **State Manager:** acts as a central data and coordination hub for the platform. It provides a first-level data management and collaborates with TrustOR to handle all TBOM-related processes, including validation and trust enforcement. It is responsible for:
 - Storing and managing security assessment results, including outputs from static and dynamic analysis tools.
 - Handling user interactions through the Dashboard, which relies on the State Manager as its backend.
 - Providing structured access to security artifacts, such as SBOMs, SSCGs, and DSCGs, and ensuring that they are available for further processing.
- **Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR):** is a component that exposes a REST API-based integration layer responsible for:
 - Validating security assessment outputs before they are incorporated into the TBOM.
 - Ensuring consistency and compliance by checking the correctness of SSCGs, DSCGs, and SBOMs.
 - Generating and updating TBOMs by consolidating validated security data from the Security Assurance.
 - Facilitating interoperability between different security validation mechanisms within RESCALE.

- **Dashboard:** Is the primary user-facing component of the RESCALE platform, providing a visual interface for interacting with security validation workflows. It acts as a frontend to the State Manager, ensuring that all interactions are traceable, intuitive, and accessible for stakeholders. Through the Dashboard, users can:
 - Monitor and review security assessments, such as SSCGs and DSCGs.
 - Track the lifecycle of TBOMs, including updates based on newly identified vulnerabilities.
 - Access historical data and reports for security compliance verification.
- **Authentication & IAM:** Given the sensitive nature of the security validation processes in RESCALE, robust access control mechanisms are enforced via authentication and authorization. The integration with an Identity and Access Management (IAM) system in this first version of the RESCALE Platform ensures that:
 - Only authorized users can interact with the security data and workflows through the Dashboard.
 - The State Manager API follows strict authentication protocols, ensuring secure communication between the assessment tools and the platform.

The Management Domain is the backbone of the Trust Orchestrator Framework, providing the coordination, validation and governance mechanisms required to establish a trusted security assurance pipeline. The following two chapters will delve into:

1. The technical implementation and deployment of the framework.
2. The integration of these components and how they interact within the platform.

3 Trust Orchestrator Framework Functionalities

This chapter details the internal structure of the Trust Orchestrator Framework, focusing on its key operational domains and their role in integrating security assurance mechanisms. It is organized as follows: Section 3.1 introduces the Management Domain, responsible for coordinating interactions between the various components. Section 3.2 describes the Security & Trust Domain, which handles validation, risk assessment, and enforcement of security policies. Finally, Section 3.3 presents the supported flows, illustrating how different processes operate within the framework to enable seamless security assurance and trust management.

3.1 Management Domain

3.1.1 Dashboard

The RESCALE dashboard is a centralized platform designed to increase trust in the software supply chain by facilitating assessments. It provides a user-friendly interface that streamlines access to testing functionalities and consolidates all relevant information in a structured manner. By offering intuitive navigation and real-time insights, the dashboard enhances the assessment process, allowing users to evaluate software and hardware components efficiently and make informed decisions.

To ensure a tailored user experience, the dashboard dynamically adapts to different user roles, providing customized features based on access levels. Users are categorized into roles such as producers and consumers, each with distinct functionalities. Producers can register software components, initiate SSCG generation, and monitor DSCG and TBOM statuses. Consumers can browse all registered components, perform dynamic analyses, and generate DSCG reports. The dashboard adjusts available options and interface elements according to the user's role, ensuring a streamlined and relevant experience for each type of user.

It includes the following key sub-components:

1. **Producer Functionality:** This component provides a dedicated interface for producers to register software components. The platform offers the necessary means to enable the producer to initiate the procedures required for SSCG generation. Producers can also monitor the statuses of the DSCG and TBOM, accessing their respective segments for detailed and actionable information.
2. **Consumer Functionality:** This component offers consumers a designated page displaying all registered software components on the platform. Consumers can select specific components to perform dynamic analyses, enabling them to assess and evaluate the components' functionality, compliance, and security posture effectively.

In the following Figure: 2, there is an overview of the Producer View in the RESCALE dashboard. The Producer View provides an overview of all functionalities available to producers within the RESCALE dashboard. This interface is designed to streamline the producer's workflow, enhance user experience, and ensure all relevant information is easily accessible.

Figure 2: Producer View of the RESCALE Dashboard

Following is a demonstration of how a component is registered using the RESCALE dashboard's producer functionality, as shown in Figure 3.

The Component Registration interface allows producers to register new software components. The clean, intuitive layout ensures that producers can complete the registration process efficiently and accurately. The registration process involves the following key steps:

- **Input Component Details:** Producers enter essential metadata such as component name, programming language, and description.
- **Validation and Compliance Check:** The system performs an initial validation to ensure all necessary fields are filled and comply with predefined requirements.
- **Submit for Registration:** Upon successful validation, the producer submits the component for registration, making it available for further analysis.

Figure 3: Component Registration Demonstration

Figure 4 shows an overview of the Consumer View in the RESCALE dashboard. The Consumer View provides consumers with a comprehensive interface to access and analyze all registered software components. To enhance ease of use, consumers can utilize the search bar and available filters to quickly locate specific components.

If an SSCG is active, consumers can browse through selected versions and view the corresponding SSCG JSON. Additionally, consumers can initiate the process of generating the DSCG report, enabling a thorough assessment of component functionality, compliance, and security posture. This interface is designed to streamline the consumer's workflow, enhance user experience, and ensure all necessary information is readily accessible.

Figure 4: Consumer View of the RESCALE Dashboard

Both producers and consumers have access to view vulnerabilities within the RESCALE dashboard. The vulnerability display is structured to ensure that key information is easily accessible and categorized effectively. Vulnerabilities are classified based on severity levels, such as critical, high, medium, and low, allowing users to prioritize risks accordingly.

The container presenting vulnerabilities includes a designated area that highlights critical fields, providing users with a general overview of the vulnerability report. Additionally, newly detected vulnerabilities are automatically linked to the corresponding software components, ensuring traceability. This structured presentation enables users to quickly assess potential security risks, track affected components, and make informed decisions regarding mitigation strategies.

Figure 5: Vulnerabilities Report

3.1.2 State Manager

3.1.2.1 Overview

The State Manager acts as the central orchestrator for the RESCALE platform's backend, handling API requests from all components outside the management layer, providing API endpoints for the rest of the RESCALE components to enable their functionalities, such as the Dashboard, the Static and Dynamic Analysis Modules, the TrustOR, and the Security Assurance pipeline, allowing for interconnectivity, and enabling the data flow inside the RESCALE platform.

The State Manager is tasked with:

1. Data Management:

- Storing and updating persistent data, such as user profiles and their associated components.
- Processing incoming requests and directing them to the appropriate modules within the RESCALE platform.

2. Action Validation:

- Ensuring the validity and integrity of actions performed within the platform.
- Utilizing multiple methods and technologies for validation, including Keycloak for authentication, JWT tokens for secure session management, cryptographic hashes for data verification, with plans to incorporate digital certificates for enhanced security in future updates.

3. Orchestration:

- Coordinating workflows between RESCALE components, such as Static and Dynamic Analysis, TrustOR, and the Security Assurance pipeline.
- Managing interdependencies and consistency, such as ensuring SSCG and DSCG serialNumbers align correctly with SBOM versions.
- Ensuring seamless data flow and processing to maintain platform consistency and enable real-time collaboration among components.

This approach enables the State Manager to act as an orchestrator, maintaining trust, security, and functionality across the entire RESCALE ecosystem.

3.1.2.2 Endpoints

The following section outlines the endpoints that facilitate interaction between users, as well as Static and Dynamic analysis components, with the RESCALE Platform in its first integrated version. Each endpoint includes a description of its functionality and is shown in Figure: 6

All the State Manager endpoints which are deemed mandatory for the End-to-End flow are keycloak protected and presented below:

- **GET** /dashboard/getUserInfo - Returns information about the authenticated user from the Keycloak token
- **POST** /repo/ComponentSet - Saves the uploaded component to MongoDB
- **GET** /dashboard/getAllUserComponents - Returns all the components of the user
- **GET** /token/<ComponentHash> - Creates and returns an Access Token to be used by SSCG and DSCG Generators
- **POST** /sscg - Receives the SSCG and SBOM reports from SSCG Generator, updates the component under test and forwards the report to TrustOR
- **GET** /sscgGetSN/<name>/<version> - Returns the serialNumber of the SSCG report for the requested version for the component <name>

GET	/dashboard/getAllUsers	Retrieve all users
GET	/dashboard/getUserInfo/{userId}	Retrieve user information
GET	/dashboard/getAllComponents/	Retrieve all components
GET	/dashboard/getAllUserComponents/{userId}	Retrieve all components of a specific user
DELETE	/dashboard/flushComponents	Flush all components
DELETE	/dashboard/flushComponent/{userId}/{componentName}	Flush a specific component of a user
POST	/repo/component	Set asset
GET	/repo/asset/{userId}/{componentId}	Retrieve asset
GET	/dashboard/sscgTokenGen	Generate SSCG token
GET	/dashboard/dscgTokenGen	Generate DSCG token
GET	/sscgGetAll	Retrieve all SSCGs from repo
GET	/sbomGetAll	Retrieve all SBOMs from repo
GET	/sscgGet/{id}	Retrieve SSCG data by Component Hash
GET	/sbomGet/{id}	Retrieve SBOM (Software Bill of Materials) data by ID
POST	/sscg	Receive SSCG and SBOM from SSCG Generator and store in repo
GET	/repo/dscg	Retrieve DSCG from repo
POST	/dscg	Retrieve DSCG from DSCG Generator
POST	/dashboard/login	Login
POST	/dashboard/register	Register a new user

Figure 6: State Manager APIs

- **GET** /sscgGet/<serialNumber> - Return the SSCG Report with the requested serial-Number
- **POST** /dscg - Receives the DSCG report from the DSCG Generator, updates the component under test and forwards the report to TrustOR
- **GET** /dscgGetSN/<name>/<version> - Returns the serialNumber of the DSCG report for the requested version for the component <name>
- **GET** /dscgGet/<serialNumber> - Return the DSCG Report with the requested serial-Number
- **POST** /tbom - Receives the TBOM report from the TrustOR and updates the component under test.
- **GET** /tbom/<serialNumber> - Returns the TBOM report with the requested serial-Number
- **POST** /SecAssurance - Receives Vulnerability Reports for a specific TBOM and updates its list of vulnerabilities

3.1.2.3 Persistent Storage

User information and its components require persistent storage for retrieval and update operations. This necessity creates the requirement for an internal database within the management module to handle users and components. The database must support structured storage, quick access, and update operations to ensure the desired functionality of the module. To meet these needs, MongoDB has been selected as the current database solution. Its document-oriented model provides flexibility in managing diverse data structures, making it well-suited for the prototype integration, as shown in figure 7. However, while MongoDB effectively serves the present requirements, its use remains subject to change. As the system grows in complexity, factors such as performance optimization, scalability, and integration with other components may give rise to a shift to a different database solution if required.

3.1.2.4 User Interaction

The State Manager handles RESCALE Users and their assets by primarily interacting with the Dashboard and the IAM Mechanism (Keycloak). Once a RESCALE user logs into the RESCALE platform through the dashboard, the State Manager authenticates their identity via Keycloak. Keycloak verifies the credentials of the user and then provides them with a JWT Token. This token is used for any further HTTP requests from this user to the State Manager, validating their identity.

The State Manager extracts the token from the headers of requests and validates it with Keycloak. If the token is valid, the request is accepted and forwarded to the appropriate module within the RESCALE Platform. The State Manager ensures that access to the RESCALE platform is appropriately restricted to authorized users. Figure: 7 depicts the procedure of user authentication via Keycloak.

Figure 7: Keycloak login validation

3.1.2.5 User Components

A RESCALE component is a software tool provided to the RESCALE platform, and serves as an actual target to perform static and dynamic code analysis (on its source code and binary files).

When a component is uploaded through the endpoint `GET /dashboard/ComponentSet`, it includes information such as the title, programming language, and description. The component is then stored in the internal database [14], as shown in [Listing 1] with a reference to the user who uploaded it.

```
{
  "title": "Test",
  "programmingLanguage": "Python",
  "description": "This is a sample component description"
}
```

Listing 1: Example of ComponentSet Request

When a user registers a component through the RESCALE Dashboard, the State Manager processes the request, extracts the required fields from the component, and appends additional information such as the component hash and userID.

The State Manager retrieves the user information by accessing Keycloak’s API at <https://iam.rescale-project.eu/realms/avt/protocol/openid-connect/userinfo>, using the authentication token provided in the Headers of the HTTP Requests. Upon providing the token, Keycloak returns relevant details about the user. Then, the State Manager checks if the user already exists by accessing the internal database with the userID as index. If no user is found, a new user is created. The response from Keycloak contains the following information: `GET /dashboard/getUserInfo/`

Example Request for User Information:

```
{
  "user": {
    "userId": "acc3f649-bbad-4220-9fa3-94bcf850672e",
    "__v": 0,
    "username": "admin"
  }
}
```

Listing 2: Response from Keycloak

By combining the information from the User’s Schema, the State Manager can now store the Component to MongoDB, with a reference to the User who uploaded it. For each component, a unique identifier is required to ensure it can be referenced and retrieved from the internal database in future operations. To achieve this, a “Hash” field is added to the component’s schema. The hash is generated using the SHA-256 algorithm by combining the component’s title and the user’s unique ID as shown in [Listing 3], ensuring that the component’s identity is unique and can be retrieved efficiently.

```
Hash = SHA256(asset.title || user.userID)
```

Listing 3: Hash Computation

This hash is then added to the component's schema before storing it in the internal database. Each user's components are linked via the `userId` field, making it easy to retrieve components based on the user's ID.

The final schema for the component, including the newly added hash field, is presented in [Listing 4]:

```
{
  "details": {
    "Title": "Test",
    "ProgrammingLanguage": "Python",
    "Description": "This is a sample component description"
  },
  "userId": "acc3f649-bbad-4220-9fa3-94bcf850672e",
  "hash":
    "d2503ffa8bfabc635434ef1bc95a3e17cf31174cf66046045e444e1ef19d4f",
  "versions": []
}
```

Listing 4: Final Component Schema

The `details` field contains all the information about the component that the user has provided. The `userId` represents the ID of the user retrieved by Keycloak. The `hash` serves as the universal unique identifier for the component. Additionally, a field that has not been presented before is the `Versions []` field, which stores information about each version of the component. This includes reports generated by SSCG, DSCG, and TBOM, as shown in the snippet [Listing 5]

3.1.2.6 Versioning

```
"versions": [
  {
    "version": "Version from SBOM",
    "statusSSCG": "SSCG Serial Number | UNAVAILABLE",
    "statusDSCG": "DSCG Serial Number | UNAVAILABLE",
    "statusTBOM": "TBOM Reference | UNAVAILABLE"
  }
]
```

Listing 5: Versions schema

As shown in snippet [Listing 5], the `version` field represents the current version of the target software tool extracted from the SBOM report. The `statusSSCG` field contains the serial number of the SSCG report generated for this version of the component; if a Static Analysis has not yet been performed, this field is set to "UNAVAILABLE." Similarly, the `statusDSCG` field stores the serial number of the DSCG report generated for this version. If a Dynamic Analysis has not yet been performed, this field is also set to "UNAVAILABLE." Finally, the `statusTBOM` field holds the serial number of the TBOM report generated for this version. If a TBOM report is not yet available, this field contains the value "UNAVAILABLE."

Security Assurance

State Manager is responsible for enabling and coordinating the Security Assurance Continuous

Monitoring flow within the RESCALE platform. The flow begins with the TrustOR initiating the creation of a new project within the Security Assurance module. This project is defined with relevant metadata, including the software name, a UUID derived from the TBOM, and other organizational details. Once the project is created, the Security Assurance module responds with a unique project identifier <projectID>, which the TrustOR uses to maintain linkage between the project and the associated TBOM.

Subsequently, the TrustOR uploads the SBOM to the Security Assurance module, ensuring it is properly formatted in CycloneDX v1.6 [20]. This file upload is tied to the <projectID> and other organizational identifiers. Upon successful upload, the TrustOR is notified of the operation's completion.

As part of the continuous monitoring process, when a new vulnerability is detected by the Security Assurance, the details are reported to the State Manager. These details include severity, CVE name, descriptions, and associated project IDs. The State Manager forwards the vulnerability details to the RESCALE Dashboard, in order to be visualised, and to the TrustOR to update the TBOM record based on the operation included inside the vulnerability message (create, retrieve, update). The TrustOR performs validation checks to ensure data integrity, verifies whether the vulnerability affects an existing TBOM, and updates its records depending on the nature of the operation.

Asynchronously, the Security Assurance Module checks for new vulnerabilities per TBOM and transmits any new finds back to the State Manager, where the process described above is repeated and the vulnerability documents with their corresponding TBOMs are updated.

3.1.3 TrustOR component

As a core unit of the **Trust Orchestrator Framework**, the **Trust Orchestrator component** (TrustOR) provides a structured interface for managing and validating security assessment artifacts within the RESCALE ecosystem. TrustOR ensures that security assessment outputs from various tools are properly validated, consolidated, and structured before they contribute to the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM).

Figure 8: TrustOR API endpoints displayed by Swagger [22]

The multiple endpoints exposed by TrustOR can be seen at Figure 8 and the following paragraphs highlight the three key API functionalities that play a crucial role in the security validation and trust establishment process:

- SBOM + SSCG submission and processing
- DSCG submission and processing
- Security Alerts handling

Note: In Figure 8, certain API endpoints appear grayed out and struck through, which indicates that they are deprecated. This is a standard visualization in Swagger (OpenAPI UI) to mark endpoints that are still part of the API definition but are no longer recommended for use. This deprecation has occurred due to replaced functionality by the SBOM+SSCG endpoint.

3.1.3.1 SBOM + SSCG Submission and Validation

The SBOM (Software Bill of Materials) and SSCG (Static Supply Chain Component Guarantee) submission API allows components from the Assessment Domain to send their validated security reports to TrustOR.

Key functionalities include:

- Receiving combined SBOM + SSCG payloads
- Validating their structure against the CycloneDX v1.6 schema [20]
- Ensuring that each submission has a unique `serialNumber` that hasn't already been added to the Platform and that it includes the Software component Name and Version
- Ensuring that the SSCG references correctly the SBOM `serialNumber`
- Storing validated SBOMs and SSCGs in the system
- Allowing retrieval of existing SBOMs and SSCGs for comparison and validation
- Returning appropriate error responses in case something goes wrong. For example, Error 400 - Bad request together with the appropriate error details is returned in case:
 - any of the Name and the Version attributes are missing
 - the SBOM `serialNumber` and the referenced SBOM `serialNumber` inside the SSCG do not match
 - any of the `serialNumbers` already exists in the database
 - the SBOM or the SSCG is not a valid CycloneDX JSON object

Endpoints:

- POST `/api/sbom_sscg/` – Submit an SBOM and an SSCG together
- GET `/api/sbom/` – Retrieve all stored SBOMs
- GET `/api/sscg/` – Retrieve all stored SSCGs
- GET `/api/sbom/{serial_number}` – Retrieve a specific SBOM by `serialNumber`
- GET `/api/sscg/{serial_number}` – Retrieve a specific SSCG by `serialNumber`

This mechanism ensures that output from the Static code Analysis is correctly formatted and integrated before further processing in the TBOM workflow.

3.1.3.2 DSCG Submission and Validation

Dynamic security assessments produce DSCGs (Dynamic Supply Chain Component Guarantees), which represent runtime testing results for software or hardware components. TrustOR validates and stores DSCGs, ensuring they are consistent with previously submitted security guarantees (SBOMs and SSCGs).

Key functionalities include:

- Accepting new DSCG submissions
- Ensuring that the DSCG references correctly the relative SSCG `serialNumber`. This includes a database lookup to check whether an SSCG can be actually retrieved with the SSCG `serialNumber` provided inside the DSCG
- Ensuring that the submitted DSCG has a unique `serialNumber` that hasn't already been added to the Platform
- Storing validated SBOMs and SSCGs in the system
- Allowing retrieval of existing DSCGs for comparison and validation
- Returning appropriate error responses in case something goes wrong. For example, Error 400 - Bad request together with the appropriate error details is returned in case:
 - the SSCG `serialNumber` referenced inside the DSCG is not found in the database and no actual SSCG is returned
 - the DSCG `serialNumber` already exists in the database
 - the DSCG is not a valid CycloneDX JSON object

Endpoints:

- POST `/api/dscg/` – Submit a new DSCG
- GET `/api/dscg/` – Retrieve all stored DSCGs
- GET `/api/dscg/{serial_number}` – Retrieve a specific DSCG by `serialNumber`

This validation process ensures alignment between static and dynamic security assessments, reinforcing the trust model used in RESCALE.

3.1.3.3 Security Alerts Processing

In addition to validating security assessment results, TrustOR also processes security alerts that may require updates or re-evaluations of existing security guarantees. These alerts are generated by the Security Assurance component and notified to TrustOR when new vulnerabilities are discovered.

Key functionalities include:

- Accepting security alerts related to existing TBOMs.
- Storing alerts along with metadata such as affected component, vulnerability ID (CVE), severity, and timestamp
- Triggering updates / revalidation workflows for impacted artifacts and proper notifications that will reach the relevant stakeholders of the vulnerability exposure, by passing through the State Manager and the Dashboard components.

Endpoint:

- POST `/api/security_alerts/` – Submit a new security alert

By integrating real-time security notifications, TrustOR ensures that previously validated TBOMs remain accurate and up-to-date, enhancing supply chain security over time.

3.2 Security & Trust Domain

Herein we describe the functionalities provided to the first integrated version of the RESCALE platform by the RESCALE security and trust components developed on WP4. The following subsections describe the functionalities provided by the Ledger Adapter (3.2.1) which, in short, provides blockchain and immutable trust storage to the RESCALE platform using the Hyperledger Besu blockchain, as discussed in D4.4. The TrustOR connects to the ledger adapter via the management module, forming the link between the trusted orchestrator and the immutable ledger. The Security Assurance mechanism (3.2.2) which is focused on the potential of vulnerabilities, attacks or intrusions into the RESCALE platform.

3.2.1 Ledger Adapter

The Ledger Adapter component serves as an abstraction layer designed to simplify blockchain write operations by encapsulating the underlying technical complexity. Without this intermediary layer, end users would need to manually execute multiple sequential tasks—including transaction creation, cryptographic signing, and network submission—to achieve ledger updates. By exposing a streamlined Python-based API, the Ledger Adapter enables developers to interact with the Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) through a unified interface, significantly reducing operational overhead.

The Ledger Adapter library provides four principal operations to facilitate blockchain interactions:

- it verifies ledger connectivity to ensure network availability before executing critical tasks;
- it supports the addition of Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM) hashes to the ledger, enabling immutable record-keeping for supply chain or software bill of materials use cases;

- it validates the integrity and authenticity of TBOM entries;
- it allows for the deprecation of obsolete TBOM records, ensuring data relevance while maintaining audit trails.

To operationalize the Ledger Adapter, developers must configure the following environment variables:

- **BESU_ENDPOINT**: Specifies the HTTP/HTTPS URL of the Hyperledger Besu node for blockchain connectivity.
- **CONTRACT_ADDR_PATH**: Defines the filesystem path to the smart contract address, which governs ledger interaction logic.
- **CONTRACT_JSON_PATH**: Points to the JSON file containing the Application Binary Interface schema for the deployed smart contract.
- **CLIENT_PRVKEY_PATH**: Contains the elliptic curve private key for transaction signing, stored in a secure file.
- **CLIENT_PUBKEY_PATH**: Provides the corresponding public key for identity verification during transaction validation.

After successful configuration, developers can execute four primary operations through the Ledger Adapter's API, each handling specific aspects of blockchain interaction.

The following sections describe each function in detail, explaining their role in blockchain interactions.

3.2.1.1 Check Besu connectivity

The adapter provides a health check mechanism to confirm node accessibility before executing critical operations. The following implementation tests connection to the Hyperledger Besu network by retrieving the chain identifier.

This function requires no input parameters and returns a string representing the blockchain network identifier in hexadecimal format:

```
get_chainid() -> str
```

Listing 6 provides an example of usage.

```
from trust_storage_client.besu_client import get_chainid

print("Check connectivity with BESU node:")
chain_id = get_chainid()
print(f"Chain ID: {chain_id}")
```

Listing 6: Checking Connectivity

3.2.1.2 Adding a Document

To permanently store document hashes on the ledger, developers utilize the document addition workflow. The process includes file ingestion, content hashing, and transaction submission.

The function accepts a document string as input and returns a dictionary containing the computed TBOM hash and transaction logs:

```
add_besu(document: str) -> dict
```

Listing 7 provides the typical structure of the output of *add_besu*:

```
{
  'hash': <Keccak-256 hash of TBOM>,
  'logs': [ // Array of emitted events
    {
      'address': <20-byte contract address>,
      'topics': [ // Array of indexed event parameters
        <Keccak-256 hash of event signature>,
        <32-bytes indexed parameter 1>,
        <32-bytes indexed parameter 2>,
        < ... >
      ],
      'data': <ABI-encoded non-indexed parameters>,
      'blockNumber': <hex string>,
      'blockHash': <32-byte hex string>,
      'transactionHash': <32-byte hex string>,
      'transactionIndex': <hex string>,
      'logIndex': <hex string>,
      'removed': <boolean>
    }
  ]
}
```

Listing 7: add_besu output dictionary structure

All hexadecimal values are represented as strings with '0x' prefix. Block and transaction positions are encoded as hex strings (e.g., '0xc' for block 12). The transaction hash uniquely identifies the transaction on the blockchain, while each log entry captures a specific event emitted during execution, with indexed parameters stored in topics and non-indexed parameters in the data field.

Listing 8 provides an example of usage.

```
from trust_storage_client.besu_client import add_besu

with open("/path/to/your/document.json") as f:
    document_content = f.read()

print("Adding document to blockchain:")
result = add_besu(document_content)
document_hash = result['hash']
print(f"Document hash: {document_hash}")
```

Listing 8: Document addition

3.2.1.3 Retrieving a Document

The retrieval mechanism enables cryptographic proof of existence checks through hash-based lookup. This function accepts a Keccak256 hash string (with 0x prefix) of the TBOM as input and returns a boolean value confirming existence. Users can obtain this hash directly from the *hash* key in the output of the *add_besu* function (see paragraph 3.2.1.2).

```
get_besu(ahash: str) -> bool
```

Listing 9 provides an example of usage.

```
from trust_storage_client.besu_client import get_besu

print("Checking if document exists:")
try:
    exists = get_besu(document_hash)
    print(f"Document exists: {exists}")
except RuntimeError as e:
    print(f"Error: {e}")
```

Listing 9: Check document hash existence

3.2.1.4 Deprecating a Document

To mark records as obsolete while maintaining audit trails, the deprecation function updates document status flags. This function accepts a Keccak256 hash string (with 0x prefix) of the TBOM as input and returns a boolean success indicator. This hash value can be directly obtained from the output of the *add_besu* function under the key 'hash' (see paragraph 3.2.1.2).

```
deprecate_besu(ahash: str) -> bool
```

Listing 10 provides an example of usage.

```
from trust_storage_client.besu_client import deprecate_besu

print("Deprecating document:")
try:
    success = deprecate_besu(document_hash)
    print(f"Document deprecated successfully: {success}")
except RuntimeError as e:
    print(f"Error: {e}")
```

Listing 10: Document deprecation

3.2.2 Security Assurance

The Continuous Security Assurance platform will provide the vulnerabilities related to the modeled cyber system. To support that, the SBOM of the cyber system, will be sent for processing over an authenticated channel.

3.2.2.1 Authentication

To get access to the Continuous Security Assurance platform, the first step is to request a token from the authentication system (see Figure 9):

Figure 9: Token API

Request:

```
{
  "client_id": "{clientId}",
  "grant_type": "password",
  "username": "{username}",
  "password": "{password}"
}
```

Response:

```
{
  "access_token": "{token}",
  "expires_in": 30,
  "refresh_expires_in": 180,
  "refresh_token": "{refreshToken}",
  "token_type": "Bearer",
  "not-before-policy": 0,
  "session_state": "{stateUUID}",
  "scope": "profile email"
}
```

3.2.2.2 Project creation

To map the identified systems' vulnerabilities, a new project will be created. Using the JSON Web Token retrieved from the aforementioned system, the following endpoint will be called:

Figure 10: Project API

Request:

```
{
  "name": "{projectName}",
  "description": "{description}",
  "organisationId": "{organisationId}",
  "status": "DEFINED",
  "activeFrom": "{currentTimestamp}",
  "visible": true,
  "isClientProject": false
}
```

Response:

```
{projectId}
```

3.2.2.3 Sending the SBOM

Finally, the last step is to process the SBOM. If the SBOM is valid and vulnerabilities are identified, they will be sent to the TrustOR system.

POST /api/core-platform/assets/import-via-sbom/organisations/{organisationId}/projects/{projectId}/owners/{ownerId} Insert assets via SBOM file

Figure 11: SBOM API

Request:

```
{
  "file": "{SBOM.json}"
}
```

Response:

```
{
  "message": "The provided SBOM is being processed"
}
```

3.3 Supported Flows

This section provides a detailed breakdown of the key operational flows within the RESCALE platform. Through a series of sequence diagrams, we illustrate the step-by-step interactions between users and the various system components, highlighting how internal processes are executed.

The goal of these diagrams is to offer a clear and structured view of how a RESCALE user (producer or consumer) can submit security assessment results (SBOMs, SSCGs, and DSCGs) and then the process of generating a Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM) is automatically triggered inside TrustOR.

Each diagram presents the exact sequence of interactions between system components such as the Dashboard, State Manager, TrustOR, and security assessment tools, ensuring that all steps necessary to achieve a secure and trusted software supply chain are fully documented.

3.3.1 Register software/hardware component

The sequence of registering a software or a hardware component includes the following actions:

- Authenticate user by providing necessary credentials to through the Dashboard UI

- Register a new component by providing the prerequisites (fields like Name, Programming language)
- Validate user information and tokens provided through the Authentication component
- Request access token for using it at the next step, the Static Analysis

At the initial stage of the TBOM creation process, the producer interacts with the Dashboard to register a new software or hardware component. The registration request is forwarded to the State Manager, which validates the user's authentication token, extracts the user's ID, and computes a Component Hash to uniquely identify the component. Once the registration is complete, the user requests an Access Token to continue further interactions with the platform. The State Manager validates the request and generates an Access Token that encapsulates the Component Hash and authentication details, to ensure a secure interaction for the next step of the flow.

Figure 12: Producer registers new component and gets access token

3.3.2 SSCG Generation & Submission

The sequence of creating and submitting the SSCG includes the following actions:

- Validate the access token.
- Parse the component's hash from the token and verify its existence.
- Extract the SBOM version and SSCG serialNumber.
- Forward the SBOM and SSCG to TrustOR to store it.
- Once successfully stored, update the component's record and notify the user.

Figure 13: Producer runs the Static Analysis and submits SBOM+SSCG

It can be easily observed by looking at the sequence diagram of Figure 13 that the State Manager and the TrustOR component are two key components in the Static Analysis workflow, responsible for validating, processing, and integrating SBOM and SSCG results into the RESCALE platform. From the previous step, it was the State Manager’s first responsibility to generate a token that will now be provided to the Static Analysis Module and will be used for validation afterwards.

The Producer who has already received this token from the State Manager via RESCALE Dash-

board, is now required to provide it to the Static Analysis Module container as input. When the Static Analysis results are received from the SSCG module, the State Manager begins by performing a series of pre-checks: It validates the access token provided in the request to ensure proper authorization and parses the token to extract the component's hash. This hash is the Universal-Unique-Identifier for the component, which is then cross-referenced to verify that the component exists in the platform's records. If the component is not found, the process is aborted immediately. Once the initial validations are complete, the State Manager retrieves essential data from the analysis results. It extracts the software version from the provided SBOM and retrieves the SSCG `serialNumber` for further validation and processing. The SBOM and SSCG are then forwarded to the TrustOR component, where a comprehensive set of checks are performed to ensure the integrity and validity of the data. TrustOR begins by verifying that the component name and version specified in the SBOM exist in the system. It then ensures that the SSCG references the SBOM's correct `serialNumber`, confirming the consistency of the results. TrustOR further checks the uniqueness of both the SBOM's `serialNumber` and the SSCG's `serialNumber` by interacting with the RESCALE Repository. These steps are essential to prevent duplication and maintain the integrity of the platform's data. Additional checks include validating the format and compliance of the SBOM and SSCG with the CycloneDX [19] specification. If any of these validations fail at any stage, the State Manager terminates the process and notifies the SSCG of the failure, forwarding the corresponding error received from the TrustOR.

Once the results pass all checks, the State Manager coordinates with TrustOR to store the data. TrustOR hashes the SBOM for secure identification and saves both the SBOM and SSCG in the RESCALE Repository. The SSCG must include the SBOM's `serialNumber` and its hash to ensure traceability and integrity. Finally, the State Manager updates the component's record with the SBOM's version and the SSCG `serialNumber`. It then sends a success response back to SSCG, and communicates this success to the user.

3.3.3 DSCG Generation & Submission

The sequence of creating and submitting the DSCG includes the following actions:

- Consumer retrieve SSCG and access token via Dashboard.
- Run Dynamic Analysis, submit DSCG report.
- Validate token, hash, and SSCG `serialNumber`.
- Extract DSSG `serialNumber`
- Forward DSCG to TrustOR to store it
- Once successfully stored, update component version with DSCG `serialNumber` and notify the user.

The DSCG Generation flow within the RESCALE platform involves a multi-stage process where the State Manager validates, processes, and integrates Dynamic Analysis results to ensure platform consistency and data integrity. As displayed in Figure 14, the process begins

Figure 14: Consumer runs the Dynamic Testing and submits DSCG

when the user logs into the platform via the Dashboard. The user’s credentials are validated by the authentication service (Keycloak), and upon successful verification, the user is granted access to the platform. The user can then either browse the Dashboard to manually select a component by filtering its name and version or use the API to request the public part of the SSCG associated with the component from the State Manager. Once the SSCG is obtained, the user requests an access token from the Dashboard, which is used for subsequent operations.

After retrieving the access token, the user downloads the Dynamic Analysis container from

Harbor (our private container registry that will be described more at section 4.1.3). The container is configured and executed with specific parameters, including the access token, the SSCG `serialNumber`, and other necessary inputs. The Dynamic Analysis process is performed, and the results are encapsulated in a DSCG report, which references the SSCG `serialNumber`. The DSCG is then submitted to the State Manager for validation and further processing. Upon receiving the DSCG, the State Manager performs a series of pre-checks. It validates the access token to confirm the request is authorized and parses it to retrieve the hash of the associated component. The State Manager verifies that a component with this hash exists in the system and checks the existence of the referenced SSCG `serialNumber`. If any of these validations fail, the process is immediately aborted, and the Dynamic Analysis Module is notified of the failure.

Next, the State Manager uses the SSCG `serialNumber` to retrieve the corresponding component version and extracts the DSCG `serialNumber` for further processing. The DSCG is then forwarded to TrustOR for additional checks. TrustOR verifies that the DSCG correctly references an existing SSCG `serialNumber` by interacting with the Repositories. It ensures the uniqueness of the DSCG `serialNumber` and validates the DSCG's compliance with CycloneDX [19] specifications, including its authenticity and integrity. If any of these checks fail, the State Manager terminates the process and notifies the SSCG of the failure.

Once all checks are successfully completed, TrustOR saves the DSCG in the Repository, associating it with the SSCG `serialNumber` and informs the State Manager of the successful operation, which updates the corresponding component version with the DSCG `serialNumber`. The State Manager sends a success response to the DSCG Generator, and communicates the result back to the user, marking the successful completion of the Dynamic Analysis process.

An important note here is that when TrustOR successfully saves the DSCG to the Repositories, it has to immediately start the TBOM creation process (which will be described in the next section). Together with the “success” message sent to the State Manager, TrustOR also sends a generated `serialNumber` which will be the one to be used within the TBOM. This is necessary because the TBOM creation process has multiple steps and the State Manager can periodically “poll” for the TBOM's status by providing this `serialNumber` to TrustOR.

3.3.4 TBOM Creation

The sequence of creating the TBOM includes the following actions:

- TrustOR combines SBOM, SSCG, DSCG, and BOV to construct TBOM.
- TrustOR stores TBOM to the Repositories and the blockchain.
- Link TBOM to a specific project within Security Assurance.
- Notify State Manager of TBOM completion and update the Dashboard.

As shown in Figure 15, the process begins with step-1 and more specifically TrustOR searching the RESCALE Repositories for specific data needed to construct the TBOM. From the previous flow, described at section 3.3.3 about the DSCG submission, TrustOR already has

Figure 15: TBOM creation process

the DSCG. What’s missing is the relative SBOM and the SSCG. These can easily be found because the DSCG references the SSCG `serialNumber` and the SSCG references the SBOM `serialNumber`. Once both artifacts are successfully located and fetched, TrustOR starts combining in one CycloneDX [19] object, the information from the SBOM, the SSCG, and the DSCG. To construct the final TBOM, TrustOR also needs to add information from the Bill of Vulnerabilities (BOV) document. Because this information will become available at (the final) step-4 of the process, TrustOR temporarily bypasses this time-consuming procedure by generating an empty BOV and adding this as a reference in the TBOM. After creating the TBOM object, TrustOR stores it in the repository, ensuring its persistence for future reference and validation. Next comes step-2 of the process, which is to insert the JSON payload of the TBOM object to the blockchain and to receive back the generated hash together with some metadata that will be kept for potential future use by TrustOR.

Once stored, TrustOR initiates the communication with the Security Assurance. For every

TBOM, a creation of a new project within the Security Assurance module is required. This generates a unique identifier, which links the TBOM to a specific context within the platform. The TrustOR then establishes a mapping between the TBOM and the projectID to maintain traceability and facilitate workflow integrations. Finally, TrustOR communicates the SBOM to Security Assurance Module, completing the information exchange required for the Security Assurance. At this point TrustOR pushes a notification to State Manager, to let it know that the TBOM creation flow has completed step-3.

Step-4 is then an asynchronous step that will take place after the Security Assurance analyzes the SBOM and reports back its findings regarding the vulnerabilities identified. This triggers a BOV update for this specific TBOM and a new blockchain transaction.

When the entire TBOM creation process is successfully concluded, the State Manager is notified about the TBOM's state. This notification ensures that the State Manager remains up-to-date on critical developments and is prepared to support subsequent platform interactions or validations involving the new TBOM. The State Manager notifies the User that the TBOM is ready and forwards the report to the Dashboard.

4 Integration Activities

This chapter details the integration activities for the Trust Orchestrator Framework, covering the technologies, testing, and deployment strategies used to ensure a seamless and secure implementation. Section 4.1 outlines key tools and technologies used, such as GitLab, Docker, Harbor, Keycloak, Jenkins and Portainer. Section 4.2 focuses on testing practices introduced, while Section 4.3 describes the deployment approach and process within the project, to provide the first integrated version of Trust Orchestrator Framework as a unified solution: the RESCALE Development Platform.

4.1 Technologies

To ensure seamless collaboration and integration across the RESCALE ecosystem, we have carefully selected industry-standard technologies that enable the deployment, management, and security of the Trust Orchestrator Framework. These technologies support automation, containerization, orchestration, authentication, and artifact management, allowing project partners to efficiently develop, test, and integrate their components.

The selected tools were chosen based on their proven reliability, scalability, and widespread adoption in software development and cybersecurity domains. They facilitate continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) of RESCALE components, enhance security assurance, and streamline service and infrastructure management. The following technologies have been selected for their role in ensuring the secure and efficient deployment of the Trust Orchestrator Framework:

- **Git & GitLab** for version control and repository management.
- **Docker** for containerization and deployment consistency.
- **Harbor** as a secure container registry.
- **Keycloak** for authentication and identity management.
- **Jenkins** for CI/CD automation and build management.
- **Portainer** for container and service orchestration.
- **RESTful APIs** used for communication with standard interfaces between RESCALE services, ensuring interoperability and scalability.
- **KrakenD** as a API Gateway for secure API communication.

Each of these tools plays a critical role in the integration process, ensuring that RESCALE's components are efficiently deployed and securely managed. In the following sections, we provide an overview of these key technologies (Section 4.1), followed by an initial approach on testing strategies used for integration (Section 4.2) and the deployment approach (Section 4.3). These sections provide a structured understanding of how the actual integration of RESCALE components is achieved.

4.1.1 Git & GitLab

Git is a distributed version control system (VCS) designed to track changes in source code efficiently. It allows multiple developers to collaborate on a project by managing branches, commits, and merges, ensuring that code changes are properly versioned and can be easily reverted if necessary. Git enables teams to work in parallel without conflicts, making it a fundamental tool for modern software development.

GitLab extends Git's functionality by providing a web-based DevOps platform that combines source code management (SCM), issue tracking, continuous integration/continuous deployment (CI/CD), and collaboration features. A private GitLab instance offers enhanced security, controlled access to source code, and the ability to enforce custom policies that align with project requirements. Organizations using Gitlab benefit from:

- Centralized repository management with granular access control.
- Integrated CI/CD pipelines to automate builds, tests, and deployments.
- Built-in issue tracking, wiki, and code review tools for streamlined collaboration.
- Self-hosting capabilities for increased privacy and compliance.

Use within RESCALE:

Figure 16 displays the home page of the private GitLab instance that has been deployed at <https://gitlab.rescale-project.eu> to facilitate collaborative software development among RESCALE partners. This self-hosted GitLab instance ensures that all source code, repositories, and development artifacts remain secure and accessible only to project members.

All project partners actively collaborate within GitLab by:

- Maintaining repositories for different components of the RESCALE ecosystem.
- Using branches for feature development, bug fixes, and experimental changes.
- Submitting merge requests (pull requests) to review and integrate changes.
- Tracking issues and discussions to manage tasks, report bugs, and document improvements.

GitLab acts as the central hub for source code versioning and collaboration in RESCALE, ensuring that all development activities follow a structured, secure, and efficient workflow. As the project evolves, GitLab will continue to serve as the foundation for managing, testing, and deploying the various components of the Trust Orchestrator Framework.

Figure 16: GitLab - list of some RESCALE code repositories

4.1.2 Docker

Docker [1] is an open-source containerization platform that enables developers to package applications along with their dependencies into lightweight, portable containers. These containers [2] ensure consistency across different environments, eliminating issues related to dependency conflicts and platform variations. By using Docker, teams can achieve a simplified and streamlined development workflow, where applications run identically on a developer’s laptop, a testing server, or a production environment. The containerized approach enhances software deployment, making it more predictable, reproducible, and scalable.

Unlike traditional virtual machines (VMs), containers share the same OS kernel, reducing overhead and improving performance. This makes them more efficient in resource utilization, leading to faster startup times and lower system requirements. Docker also integrates with orchestration tools like Kubernetes and Docker Swarm, enabling teams to manage, scale, and automate containerized applications efficiently. Additionally, through Docker Compose, multiple containers can be defined and deployed together, ensuring seamless multi-container application management.

Use within RESCALE:

Docker is a widely used containerization technology that enables the packaging, distribution, and execution of applications in a lightweight, portable, and consistent manner. Thus, it has played a crucial role within RESCALE, serving as the foundation for collaboration, develop-

ment, and deployment. By leveraging Docker, RESCALE partners have been able to ensure consistency across different environments, from local development machines to virtual machines (VMs) hosting critical CI/CD services.

By taking advantage of its “multi-platform” capabilities, Docker can provide a standardized runtime environment, allowing developers to work with the same application stacks regardless of their operating system or hardware configuration. It runs seamlessly on developer laptops, ensuring that components and services behave identically across different teams. At the same time, it powers the CI/CD infrastructure, where our continuous integration and testing workflows are executed on VM-based environments. Furthermore, the Static Code Analysis Module and the Dynamic Testing Module which are the testing tools provided by RESCALE, leverage a Docker-based deployment/testing environment to ensure modularity and reproducibility.

By standardizing on Docker, RESCALE has created a highly flexible and efficient ecosystem, enabling partners to collaborate seamlessly while ensuring that all services remain portable, scalable, and easy to maintain.

4.1.3 Harbor

Harbor [7] is an open-source, cloud-native container registry that provides a secure and scalable way to store, manage, and distribute container images. It extends the functionality of the default Docker Registry by offering advanced features such as vulnerability scanning, role-based access control (RBAC), and content signing. These features help organizations enforce security policies, ensuring that only trusted and verified images are used in production environments. Harbor also supports multi-tenancy, allowing teams to manage multiple projects with isolated access controls.

One of the key advantages of Harbor is its ability to replicate container images across multiple registries, facilitating multi-region deployments and disaster recovery strategies. It integrates seamlessly with identity providers like LDAP and OIDC, enabling centralized authentication and access management. By using Harbor, organizations can enhance container security, maintain compliance with industry standards, and improve the overall reliability of their software supply chain.

Use within RESCALE:

Harbor serves as our centralized private container registry where partners continuously push and manage their container images. It has been instrumental in streamlining development workflows, allowing each partner to work independently by utilizing separate projects, while also facilitating collaboration through shared repositories (see Figure: 17). By organizing container images into project-based workspaces, partners could maintain isolated environments when needed while still benefiting from shared resources for joint efforts.

Harbor also helped the consortium solve the challenge of having multiple developers working on different CPU architectures. For example, developers using MacBooks with arm64-based machines could build and push “multi-platform” container images that were later pulled and executed by other developers who worked on amd64-based systems and vice versa. This capability ensured that all RESCALE components could be tested and deployed across different hardware architectures without compatibility issues. A small example of a “multi-platform”

Figure 17: Harbor - Projects view

image is shown at Figure 18.

Additionally, Harbor’s integration with Keycloak allowed user management based on role-based access control (RBAC). By grouping users into “teams” and later assigning teams to “projects”, it provided both isolation when needed and shared access when collaboration was required. This approach significantly improved the security and organization of RESCALE’s development process, ensuring that partners could work efficiently without interfering with each other’s environments while still having the ability to collaborate on shared deployments. An indicative screenshot is provided by Figure 19.

4.1.4 Keycloak / IAM

Keycloak [24] is an open-source Identity and Access Management (IAM) solution designed to provide secure authentication and authorization services. It supports Single Sign-On (SSO), allowing users to log in once and gain access to multiple applications without needing to re-enter credentials. Keycloak integrates with various authentication protocols, including OAuth2 [6], OpenID Connect [17], and SAML [16], making it a versatile choice for managing user identities across different platforms. It also provides multi-factor authentication (MFA) [23], social login integration, and federation with external identity providers such as LDAP [8] and Active Directory [12].

By centralizing identity management, Keycloak simplifies user administration and enhances security in distributed environments. Organizations can define fine-grained access control policies, ensuring that users and applications have appropriate permissions. Additionally, Keycloak provides session management, user self-service options, and audit logging, helping organizations maintain compliance and improve security posture. Its integration capabilities make it an essential tool for modern cloud-native applications requiring robust authentication mecha-

Figure 18: Harbor - Image with multi-platform artifacts

nisms.

Use within RESCALE:

Within the RESCALE project, Keycloak plays a crucial role in identity and access management (IAM), ensuring secure authentication and authorization across different tools and platform components. RESCALE utilizes two separate Keycloak instances, each serving a distinct purpose.

The first Keycloak instance (accessible at: <https://keycloak.rescale-project.eu>) is dedicated to managing access to the CI/CD tools, including Jenkins, Harbor, and Portainer. All users requesting access to the CI/CD infrastructure are registered in this Keycloak instance and assigned to specific groups based on their roles. The group functionality is leveraged for authorization, ensuring that users have the appropriate level of access to each service. The integration of Jenkins, Harbor, and Portainer with Keycloak via OpenID Connect (OIDC) enables single sign-on (SSO), centralized user management, and streamlined role-based access control (RBAC). In Figure 20 the Keycloak Groups created can be seen and by taking a closer look, they are identical to the ones displayed to the Harbor relative screenshot (see Figure: 19).

The second Keycloak instance (accessible at: <https://iam.rescale-project.eu>) is used for RESCALE platform users, ensuring secure access to core platform components. Key RESCALE services, such as the Dashboard and State Manager, authenticate and authorize users through this instance.

By implementing Keycloak in this way, RESCALE ensures a clear separation of concerns between infrastructure access (CI/CD tools) and platform-level authentication (RESCALE services). This setup provides secure, flexible, and scalable identity management, enabling both independent workflows and controlled collaboration within the project.

While Keycloak supports advanced identity management features, such as Active Directory integration, multi-factor authentication (MFA), and fine-grained access control mechanisms,

Figure 19: Harbor - User Groups view

these capabilities are not currently planned for implementation in the RESCALE Platform. The current authentication strategy focuses on streamlined user access to RESCALE services without the complexity of external directory synchronization or additional authentication layers. Future iterations of the platform may revisit these enhancements based on project needs and security requirements.

4.1.5 Jenkins

Jenkins [3] is an open-source automation server that enables CI/CD by automating various stages of the software development life-cycle. It allows developers to build, test, and deploy applications more efficiently, reducing manual errors and accelerating development cycles. With Jenkins, teams can define automated workflows using pipeline scripts, ensuring a consistent and repeatable deployment process. The platform supports a vast ecosystem of plugins, making it highly customizable and adaptable to different development environments.

Jenkins integrates seamlessly with popular tools such as Git, Docker, Kubernetes, and cloud platforms, allowing organizations to streamline DevOps practices. It supports distributed builds, enabling parallel execution of tasks to speed up the development process. Additionally, Jenkins provides real-time monitoring, logging, and notification capabilities, helping teams identify and resolve issues quickly. By automating CI/CD workflows, Jenkins enhances software quality, improves deployment efficiency, and supports agile development methodologies.

Figure 20: Keycloak - User Groups view

Use within RESCALE:

Within the RESCALE project, Jenkins has been integrated as the central CI/CD automation tool, providing a structured and scalable approach to continuous integration and continuous deployment (CI/CD). While the technology is fully set up and operational, widespread adoption by all partners is still in progress.

The Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR) component has already established the first working Jenkins pipeline, setting the paradigm for future CI/CD workflows within RESCALE. The TrustOR pipeline is automatically triggered by a GitLab push to the master branch, executing the following steps:

1. **Unit Testing** – Running automated tests to ensure code correctness.
2. **Docker Image Build** – Creating a multi-platform container image.
3. **Image Push to Harbor** – Storing the containerized component in the Harbor registry for easy access and deployment.
4. **Deployment to a Development Server (optionally)** – If all previous steps succeed, the latest version can automatically be deployed to a development environment.

Figure: 21 shows a series of successful builds that took place for the Trust Orchestrator component.

This initial setup demonstrates the benefits of Jenkins within RESCALE, showcasing how automation can improve development efficiency, ensure consistency, and streamline deployments. Over the coming months, the remaining RESCALE components will be on-boarded to Jenkins, with partners expected to adopt similar pipelines for:

Figure 21: Jenkins - Example of a TrustOR pipeline

- Automated unit and functional testing.
- Docker image builds and deployments.
- Future integration testing across multiple components.

By gradually expanding its usage, Jenkins will become a key enabler of quality assurance and DevOps practices in RESCALE, ensuring that all components follow a structured, automated, and reliable development life-cycle.

4.1.6 Portainer

Portainer [18] is an open-source container management platform that provides an intuitive web-based interface for managing Docker environments. It simplifies container deployment, monitoring, and lifecycle management, making it accessible to both beginners and experienced DevOps teams. Portainer allows users to oversee all aspects of their containerized applications, including containers, images, volumes, networks, and access controls. With support for Docker Swarm, Kubernetes, and standalone Docker instances, it provides a centralized platform for container orchestration.

One of Portainer's key advantages is its lightweight architecture, as it runs as a single container that can be easily deployed in any Docker environment. It enhances operational efficiency by offering role-based access control (RBAC), real-time container insights, and resource management capabilities. Portainer also integrates with CI/CD pipelines and third-party tools, enabling

automated deployments and streamlined container operations. By providing a user-friendly interface, Portainer reduces the complexity of container management, making it an essential tool for teams adopting containerized workflows.

Use within RESCALE:

Within the RESCALE project, Portainer has been deployed as the primary container management tool, offering a centralized interface for monitoring and managing containerized services. It is integrated alongside CI/CD services, providing visibility and control over the execution environments used for development, testing, and deployment.

The main Portainer instance runs alongside the other CI/CD services and is configured to manage multiple environments. At present, three distinct environments are available within Portainer:

1. **CI/CD Environment** – This environment represents the VM hosting RESCALE’s actual CI/CD services. As seen in Figure: 22 it displays the containers for Jenkins, Harbor, Keycloak, Portainer, plus some other services supporting the whole setup. Access to this environment is restricted to the admin group, ensuring that only authorized users can view and manage these critical infrastructure services.
2. **Testing Environment** – This environment corresponds to the VM used by Jenkins for building, testing, and running containers. It provides insight into the containerized execution of unit tests, functional tests, and build pipelines, allowing developers to monitor and troubleshoot their CI/CD workflows.
3. **TrustOR Environment** – This environment represents the VM where Jenkins deploys and runs a development version of the entire RESCALE Platform. It enables developers to test the whole Trust Orchestrator Framework in an isolated development setting, ensuring that new changes can be validated before further deployment.

By centralizing container management, Portainer provides better visibility, streamlined monitoring, and controlled access to different RESCALE environments. Similarly to Harbor, which was described previously in this chapter, integrating with Keycloak and utilizing OpenID Connect flows, multiple RESCALE developers can use their CI/CD accounts to access Portainer and control the life-cycle of their containerized applications via a simple user interface, without the need to be granted direct SSH access to the project’s infrastructure. (more at: 4.3.1 Infrastructure View). As development progresses, it will continue to play a key role deployment management, ensuring that partners can effectively oversee and maintain their containerized services.

4.1.7 RESTful APIs

Representational State Transfer (REST) [5] is an architectural style used for building scalable and interoperable web services. RESTful APIs follow a client-server model, where clients send HTTP requests [4] to interact with resources exposed by the server. These APIs use standard HTTP methods such as:

Name	State	Filter	Quick Actions	Stack	Image	Created	IP Address	Published Ports	Ownership
harbor-core	healthy		[Stop] [Restart] [Pause] [Resume] [Remove]	harbor	goharbor/harbor-core:v2.11.0	2024-08-14 11:30:43	172.18.0.12	-	administrators
harbor-db	healthy		[Stop] [Restart] [Pause] [Resume] [Remove]	harbor	goharbor/harbor-db:v2.11.0	2024-08-14 11:30:43	172.18.0.10	-	administrators
harbor-jobservice	healthy		[Stop] [Restart] [Pause] [Resume] [Remove]	harbor	goharbor/harbor-jobservice:v2.11.0	2024-08-14 11:30:43	172.18.0.13	-	administrators
harbor-log	healthy		[Stop] [Restart] [Pause] [Resume] [Remove]	harbor	goharbor/harbor-log:v2.11.0	2024-08-14 11:30:43	172.18.0.6	0.0.0.0:1514:10514	administrators
harbor-portal	healthy		[Stop] [Restart] [Pause] [Resume] [Remove]	harbor	goharbor/harbor-portal:v2.11.0	2024-08-14 11:30:43	172.18.0.7	-	administrators
jenkins	running		[Stop] [Restart] [Pause] [Resume] [Remove]	jenkins	jenkins/jenkins:sls	2024-08-14 11:30:40	172.18.0.4	-	administrators
keycloak	running		[Stop] [Restart] [Pause] [Resume] [Remove]	keycloak	quay.io/keycloak/keycloak:22.0	2024-08-14 11:30:47	172.18.0.16	-	administrators
keycloak-postgres	running		[Stop] [Restart] [Pause] [Resume] [Remove]	keycloak	postgres:16	2024-08-14 11:30:47	172.18.0.15	-	administrators
letsencrypt-proxy	running		[Stop] [Restart] [Pause] [Resume] [Remove]	proxy-server	jjcs/letsencrypt-nginx-proxy-companion:stable	2024-08-14 11:30:40	172.18.0.2	-	administrators
nginx	healthy		[Stop] [Restart] [Pause] [Resume] [Remove]	harbor	goharbor/nginx-photov2.11.0	2024-08-14 11:30:43	172.18.0.14	0.0.0.0:8080	administrators
nginx-proxy	running		[Stop] [Restart] [Pause] [Resume] [Remove]	proxy-server	juwilder/nginx-proxy:1.5-alpine	2024-08-14 11:30:40	172.18.0.3	0.0.0.0:443:443	administrators
portainer	running		[Stop] [Restart] [Pause] [Resume] [Remove]	portainer	portainer/portainer-ce	2024-08-14 11:30:41	172.18.0.5	-	administrators
redis	healthy		[Stop] [Restart] [Pause] [Resume] [Remove]	harbor	goharbor/redis-photov2.11.0	2024-08-14 11:30:43	172.18.0.9	-	administrators
registry	healthy		[Stop] [Restart] [Pause] [Resume] [Remove]	harbor	goharbor/registry-photov2.11.0	2024-08-14 11:30:43	172.18.0.11	-	administrators
registryctl	healthy		[Stop] [Restart] [Pause] [Resume] [Remove]	harbor	goharbor/harbor-registryctl:v2.11.0	2024-08-14 11:30:43	172.18.0.8	-	administrators

Figure 22: Portainer - list of containers running the CI/CD services

- GET - Retrieve data from the server
- POST - Submit new data to be processed
- PUT/PATCH - Update existing resources
- DELETE - Remove a resource

RESTful APIs rely on a stateless communication model, meaning each request is independent and contains all necessary information to be processed. This approach enhances scalability and flexibility, making RESTful services well-suited for distributed systems like RESCALE.

Additionally, RESTful APIs commonly use JSON as the data exchange format, ensuring lightweight and human-readable communication between services. Authentication and authorization mechanisms, such as OAuth 2.0 or API tokens, are typically enforced to protect sensitive data and prevent unauthorized access.

Use within RESCALE:

In RESCALE, RESTful APIs serve as the primary communication mechanism between components. They provide a simple and widely adopted approach for exchanging data, making integration between services straightforward and maintainable.

For now, RESTful APIs act as the “glue” of the system, facilitating interactions between key components such as the State Manager, TrustOR, and security assessment tools. This approach allows for rapid development and flexibility, ensuring that security validation workflows function smoothly.

However, as RESCALE evolves, we remain open to exploring more advanced communication mechanisms if needed. Future iterations may incorporate event-driven architectures or message queuing systems to enhance scalability and performance.

Figure 23: Portainer - The 3 environments currently provided through 3 independent VMs

4.1.8 KrakenD

KrakenD [10] is a high performance API gateway that provides organizations with the ability to efficiently manage, secure, and consolidate their backend services. By acting as a single entry point between clients and multiple underlying APIs, KrakenD streamlines request routing, protocol translation, and response aggregation while minimizing latency and complexity. Its flexible, configuration-driven approach eliminates the need for custom coding, making it simpler and faster to define endpoints, apply authentication and authorization rules, implement caching, and perform load balancing.

Use within RESCALE:

In the RESCALE project, KrakenD will serve as the principal exposed service, functioning as the interface between the frontend and the backend components. All client requests originating from the frontend will be directed to KrakenD, which will handle the authentication and authorization processes through the use of a Keycloak service, thereby ensuring secure access. Upon successful authentication, KrakenD will then forward the requests to the State Manager component. The State Manager will be responsible for performing all routing and coordinating the necessary backend services to fulfill the client's requests. By using KrakenD for this purpose, the system ensures a streamlined, secure, and efficient communication flow, while the State Manager handles the underlying logic and service orchestration. Additionally, KrakenD is capable of integrating bot detection mechanisms, providing protection against malicious or unwanted traffic, and enhancing the overall security of the system. Furthermore, the support for rate limiting, caching, and circuit breaking serves to reinforce the reliability and resilience of the system by mitigating the effects of overload scenarios and reducing latency.

4.2 Testing

Testing plays a critical role in the CI/CD pipeline, ensuring that each change introduced into the system is functional, stable, and does not break existing workflows. By integrating automated testing into the development process, teams can detect errors early, reduce manual effort, and maintain a high-quality codebase.

In RESCALE, testing practices are being progressively introduced across all components to improve the reliability and maintainability of the platform. The goal is to establish a structured approach, where each component follows a consistent testing strategy before being deployed.

4.2.1 TrustOR Pipeline Example

Figure 24: Failing Jenkins pipeline followed by a successful one

To illustrate the importance of automated testing, we present an example from the TrustOR component, which has adopted unit testing within its CI/CD pipeline. The following sequence demonstrates how testing helps prevent faulty code from being deployed:

1. A developer pushes a faulty change to the TrustOR repository.
2. The Jenkins pipeline runs automatically, triggering unit tests for TrustOR.
3. The pipeline fails, highlighting issues in the code that need to be fixed (notice the “red” boxes in Figure 24). The faulty container image was never built and pushed to our registry.
4. The developer corrects the issue and pushes the fix.

5. A new pipeline runs successfully, ensuring the component is now stable (notice the “green” boxes of the last pipeline in Figure 24). The pipeline also shows that this working container image passed the unit tests and was built and pushed to our registry.

4.2.2 Expanding Testing to Other RESCALE Components

As the project progresses, this testing methodology will be adopted across all components to strengthen the platform’s development lifecycle. Each component will:

- Introduce unit and functional testing pipelines, ensuring that changes do not introduce regressions.
- Expand towards integration and end-to-end testing, validating interactions between components.

By incorporating automated testing at multiple levels, we will ensure that the Trust Orchestrator Framework evolves into a stable, reliable, and production-ready security platform.

4.3 Deployment

This section covers deployment processes, focusing on two key aspects: (1) the setup of the CI/CD infrastructure, which facilitates collaboration, development and integration across RESCALE components, and (2) the deployment of the first integrated version of the Trust Orchestrator Framework. The CI/CD environment ensures efficient development workflows, while the framework deployment establishes the foundation for providing the framework as a unified platform.

4.3.1 Infrastructure View

For the project’s needs, we operate on a distributed virtualized infrastructure, currently consisting of four Virtual Machines (VMs), each dedicated to specific functionalities and depicted in Figure 25. This infrastructure setup ensures a clear separation of concerns, supporting CI/CD, development, authentication, and testing workflows. Below is an overview of each VM and its role within the project.

VM-1: CI/CD & Container Management

VM-1 serves as the central hub for Continuous Integration and Deployment (CI/CD) services, hosting key tools that automate builds, tests, and container image management. It runs:

- **NGINX** [15] - A robust reverse proxy for exposing the underlying CI/CD services in a secure way and with certificates provided by Let’s Encrypt [11].
- **Jenkins** - Automates software builds, testing, and deployment.

Figure 25: Infrastructure View

- **Harbor** - A private container registry for storing and managing Docker images.
- **Keycloak** - Handles authentication for CI/CD services via OpenID Connect (OIDC).
- **Portainer** - Provides a web-based interface for monitoring and managing Docker containers.

This VM is accessible to developers via the following addresses:

- <https://keycloak.rescale-project.eu>
- <https://jenkins.rescale-project.eu>
- <https://harbor.rescale-project.eu>
- <https://portainer.rescale-project.eu>

It is also being accessed by our GitLab, whenever a developer sets up a specific Web-hook. This way, events taking place inside GitLab can be propagated to Jenkins and automatic pipelines can get triggered. VM-1 enables automated software delivery, allowing developers to build, test, and push multi-platform Docker images efficiently.

VM-2: Build & Testing Resources

VM-2 is used for testing and deployments, acting as an execution environment for CI/CD workflows. It provides:

- Dedicated resources for builds and tests, ensuring scalability.
- Docker runtime for running containerized workloads.
- Portainer integration for monitoring and managing test environments.

This VM supports Jenkins pipeline execution, allowing developers to test components in isolation before deploying them into a full development environment.

VM-3: RESCALE Development Platform

VM-3 hosts the core RESCALE development environment, where key platform components are deployed for testing and validation. It includes:

- State Manager (SM) – Orchestrates platform data and user-platform interactions.
- Dashboard – The web interface for users to interact with RESCALE.
- Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR) component – Manages SBOM, SSCG, DSCG and TBOM workflows.
- MongoDB [14] & Mongo Express [13] – The database backend for storing platform data and a web-based administrative interface for easily viewing, querying, and managing them.
- NGINX – A robust reverse proxy for exposing the underlying services in a secure way and with certificates provided by Let's Encrypt.

This VM is accessible to RESCALE users via:

- <https://dashboard.dev.rescale-project.eu>
- <https://sm.dev.rescale-project.eu>

VM-3 serves as the testing ground for platform features, enabling developers to interact with deployed services in a controlled development environment.

The first three VMs which have been described are interconnected and integrated

VM-4: Identity and Access Management (IAM)

VM-4 is dedicated to user authentication and identity management for the RESCALE platform. It runs a separate Keycloak instance, accessible at:

- <https://iam.rescale-project.eu>

This instance is currently used by two crucial platform components, the Dashboard and the State Manager (SM), to authenticate and authorize users, ensuring controlled access to platform resources.

The first three virtual machines (VM-1, VM-2, and VM-3) are interconnected and integrated as part of the CI/CD infrastructure. Specifically, VM-1 hosts the Jenkins services, while VM-2 and VM-3 run Jenkins agents that provide their computational resources for executing pipeline jobs. Similarly, Portainer services run on VM-1 and the Docker environments from VM-2 and VM-3 are integrated by providing secure access to their respective Docker daemon services. This close integration ensures a coordinated execution of CI/CD workflows across these machines. On the other hand, VM-4 operates independently and is not involved in the CI/CD setup. This is visually represented in Figure 25, where VM-4 is depicted separately, distinguishing it from the tightly coupled Jenkins-based infrastructure.

4.3.2 RESCALE Platform Deployment

To facilitate the development and integration of RESCALE services, the project partners established a development deployment strategy, ensuring a smooth transition from local testing to a shared deployment environment. This process was carried out in incremental steps, leading to a fully functional deployment on VM-3.

Step 1: Preparing the Development Workflow

Initially, all partners were onboarded with the containerization workflow, learning how to push container images to Harbor, the project's private container registry. This step ensured that each partner could independently build and publish their service images, making them available for deployment.

Step 2: Collaborative Repository for Deployment

To streamline deployment, a GitLab repository named “dev-platform” was created accessible at <https://gitlab.rescale-project.eu/rescale/dev-platform>. This repository contains a Docker Compose configuration file (`docker-compose.yaml`), which defines the services necessary for the RESCALE platform and a version of it can be found in the Appendix: RESCALE Development Platform - Docker compose file with yaml format.

- The Docker Compose file references pre-built images from Harbor, allowing partners to assemble and launch the platform effortlessly.
- This approach mimicks an off-the-shelf deployment, where each service is pre-packaged and ready to use, ensuring rapid setup.

Step 3: Local Testing and Validation

Partners initially deployed the RESCALE platform on their local machines (laptops/workstations) using Docker Compose.

- This setup allowed individual teams to validate the services in isolation and ensure they worked as expected while trying to develop and integrate.
- It provided a controlled environment for debugging and testing, reducing the risk of issues in later deployments.

Step 4: Moving to a Shared Development Environment on VM-3

Once the local deployments proved stable and reliable, the project team decided to start deploying the platform on VM-3, making it accessible in a shared development environment.

1. Subdomains & NGINX Reverse Proxy Setup:

- Two subdomains have been registered, one for the RESCALE Dashboard and another for the State Manager, as previously mentioned in the VM-3 description.
- An NGINX reverse proxy is deployed on VM-3 to manage incoming requests, directing traffic only to the necessary services.
- “Let’s Encrypt” SSL/TLS certificates ensure secure communication over HTTPS.

2. Container Networking & service reachability:

- The RESCALE services are deployed within their own isolated Docker network, utilizing Docker’s internal DNS resolution for inter-container communication.
- Services can reach each other by using their container names, eliminating the need for manually defining network addresses.
- External access is strictly controlled:
 - Only ports 80 and 443 are open to external traffic.
 - NGINX handles all incoming requests, forwarding traffic only to the required services.
 - All other services remain completely inaccessible from outside.

3. CI/CD Automation with GitLab, Jenkins, Harbor & Portainer

- Jenkins pipelines have been configured to trigger deployments of the new versions of services when they are pushed to Harbor (as seen in Figure 26).
- GitLab, combined with Jenkins, facilitate the seamless rollout of updates with minimal manual intervention.
- Portainer provides a visual interface to monitor and manage the deployed containers on VM-3 (as depicted in Figure 27).

Outcome & Benefits

- This incremental deployment strategy ensured that the RESCALE platform was thoroughly tested before moving to a shared VM.
- The combination of containerization, reverse proxying, and CI/CD pipelines resulted in a stable and easily maintainable development deployment.
- Developers can now spin up or update the RESCALE platform on VM-3 with a push of a button, streamlining the development process and accelerating integration efforts.

Figure 26: Jenkins: Pipeline for deploying the "dev-platform"

Figure 27: Portainer: Containers running the "dev-platform" services

5 Conclusions & Future Steps

This chapter summarizes the challenges encountered during the initial implementation of the Trust Orchestrator Framework, presents key lessons learned, and outlines the next steps toward a production-ready RESCALE platform. The experience gained from the design, integration, and early deployment phases will serve as the foundation for further refinement and enhancement of the system.

5.1 Challenges & Lessons Learned

Throughout the development of the Trust Orchestrator Framework, we encountered several technical and organizational challenges that shaped our approach. The following key challenges and lessons learned highlight the critical areas that required iterative improvements and collaborative problem-solving.

Defining an End-to-End Flow for Implementation

One of the initial challenges was translating the Logical View of RESCALE's architecture and the sequence diagrams from D2.5 – High-Level Architecture (first version) into a concrete, end-to-end implementation flow. While the conceptual models provided an excellent starting point, we realized that a specific level of technical detail was required before development could begin.

The solution was to organize a series of online workshops where we meticulously broke down each step of the process. These sessions not only helped refine the specifications but also facilitated detailed discussions on the internal workflows of some components, ensuring that all development teams had a clear and actionable road-map for implementation.

Handling Multi-Platform Docker Image Compatibility

A common misconception in containerized environments is that Docker solves all compatibility issues, but in reality, containers must be built for the specific CPU architecture of the deployment environment. This became a challenge in RESCALE, as partners were developing on different system architectures (x86, ARM, etc.), leading to issues where incompatible images were being deployed, causing failures during execution.

For example, during early integration tests, a Dashboard container built on an ARM-based development machine (Apple MacBook with M4 chip [9]) was deployed to an x86-based test environment, resulting in a runtime failure where the container would not start, displaying an `Exec format error`. This issue delayed testing and required debugging efforts to trace back the root cause, as some partners were unaware that Docker images are architecture-dependent by default.

This challenge was quickly identified and addressed through the implementation of multi-platform builds and proper container registry management using Harbor. By ensuring that all Docker images were built with architecture-specific tags, we prevented compatibility issues and ensured that any deployment could seamlessly pull the correct version of each service.

Navigating the Dynamic Nature of CycloneDX format

CycloneDX, the SBOM, SSCG, DSCG, BOV and TBOM specification used in RESCALE, is highly dynamic and evolving, providing a wide range of capabilities for supply chain security management. However, since the project team was both developing the system and simultaneously learning best practices for using CycloneDX, it required effort to define consistent conventions that would allow tools to exchange these files effectively.

We focused on progressive learning and iterative adjustments, refining how we structured CycloneDX data models and ensuring that components could interoperate smoothly within the RESCALE platform. This remains an ongoing effort as we gain further experience and standardize best practices.

5.2 Conclusions

The first version of the Trust Orchestrator Framework marks a significant milestone in the RESCALE project. The integration of key components, the deployment of a development platform, and the establishment of a CI/CD workflow have laid a solid foundation for further advancements.

Key takeaways from this phase include:

- Successful integration of multiple partner-developed components into a unified system.
- Implementation of CI/CD pipelines, enabling streamlined deployments and automated testing.
- Refinement of deployment strategies, ensuring multi-platform compatibility and secure access control.
- Deepened understanding of how CycloneDX can be effectively leveraged in the project.

These achievements demonstrate that the RESCALE platform is progressing towards a fully operational state, but also highlight areas that require further refinement and optimization.

5.3 Future Steps

The next phase of the project will focus on scaling up development efforts, enhancing automation, and moving towards a production-ready deployment. This work aligns with the project's final integration milestone (Number 12, with due date: month 32), which marks the completion of the RESCALE Trust Orchestrator framework, including all primitives and services.

As part of this milestone, *Deliverable D5.2 – Trust Orchestrator (final version)* will be produced, presenting the fully integrated version of the framework. This final iteration will incorporate refinements based on insights gained during the initial implementation, testing, and validation phases, ensuring the framework meets the functional, security, and scalability requirements for real-world deployment.

The following key areas will be prioritized in this phase:

Expanding CI/CD Adoption & Best Practices

- Onboard more partners into the CI/CD system, ensuring all teams use automated workflows for building and testing their components.
- Encourage best practices in CI/CD pipelines, including automated unit and functional testing for all RESCALE services.

Advancing automated End-to-End Testing & Integration

- Implement pipelines for automated end-to-end testing, allowing us to validate the entire platform's functionality with minimal manual intervention.
- Ensure seamless integration testing between interconnected services, identifying and resolving issues early in the development cycle.

Optimizing Deployment & Moving Toward a Production-Ready Platform

- Refine the deployment process, improving scalability, security, and reliability.
- Transition towards a fully automated deployment system, ensuring that a production-ready RESCALE platform can be deployed with minimal effort.
- Improve monitoring and observability tools, providing deeper insights into system health, security, and performance.

Towards the Final Version: Cross-Work-Package Collaboration

This deliverable represents the first integrated version of the Trust Orchestrator Framework. As we work towards the final version in the upcoming months, a cross-work-package collaboration will be essential. The focus will be on strengthening security and making further progress in trust establishment, closely following the specifications emerging from WP4.

- WP4 is defining the trust models and security requirements, which will serve as the foundation for the next integration phase.
- WP3, responsible for testing tools, will need to ensure that their outputs align with these specifications.
- WP5, which focuses on integration and orchestration, will adapt to these evolving requirements, ensuring that components are integrated in a more secure and trusted manner.

This second iteration of integration will not only enhance the security and trust mechanisms but may also lead to changes in the way components interact within the Trust Orchestrator Framework. As the platform matures, adhering to the refined specifications will ensure that RESCALE delivers a robust, secure, and fully operational solution.

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6 Appendix

6.1 RESCALE Development Platform - Docker compose file

```
services:

  mongodb:
    image: mongodb/mongodb-community-server:7.0.12-ubi8
    container_name: mongodb
    environment:
      MONGO_INITDB_ROOT_USERNAME: root
      MONGO_INITDB_ROOT_PASSWORD: pass
    ports:
      - "127.0.0.1:27017:27017"
    restart: always
    networks:
      - rescale-net
    labels:
      io.portainer.accesscontrol.teams: rescale-all

  mongo-express:
    image: mongo-express
    container_name: mongo-express
    environment:
      ME_CONFIG_MONGODB_SERVER: mongodb
      ME_CONFIG_MONGODB_URL: mongodb://mongodb:27017
      ME_CONFIG_BASICAUTH_USERNAME: root
      ME_CONFIG_BASICAUTH_PASSWORD: pass
      ME_CONFIG_MONGODB_ADMINUSERNAME: root
      ME_CONFIG_MONGODB_ADMINPASSWORD: pass
    ports:
      - "127.0.0.1:8081:8081"
    restart: always
    depends_on:
      - mongodb
    networks:
      - rescale-net
    labels:
      io.portainer.accesscontrol.teams: rescale-all

  trustor:
    image: harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/trustor:latest
    container_name: trustor
    environment:
      MONGO_HOST: mongodb
      STATE_MANAGER_URL: http://state-manager:3000
    ports:
      - "127.0.0.1:8000:8000"
    restart: always
    depends_on:
      - mongodb
    networks:
      - rescale-net
    labels:
      io.portainer.accesscontrol.teams: rescale-all
```

```
state-manager:
  image: harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/state_manager:latest
  container_name: state-manager
  pull_policy: always
  restart: always
  environment:
    NODE_ENV: development
    TRUSTOR_API_SSCG_URL: http://trustor:8000/api/sscg
    TRUSTOR_API: http://trustor:8000/api/sbom_sscg
    TRUSTOR_API_SBOM_URL: http://trustor:8000/api/sbom
    TRUSTOR_API_DSCG_URL: http://trustor:8000/api/dscg
    MONGO_URL: 'mongodb://root:*****@mongodb:27017/admin'
    MONGO_USERNAME: root
    MONGO_PASSWORD: *****
    KEYCLOAK_URL: https://iam.rescale-project.eu
    KEYCLOAK_REALM: avt
    KEYCLOAK_CLIENT_ID: state_manager
    KEYCLOAK_CLIENT_SECRET: *****
  ports:
    - '127.0.0.1:3000:3000'
  networks:
    - rescale-net
  depends_on:
    - mongodb
  labels:
    io.portainer.accesscontrol.teams: rescale-all

avt:
  image: 'harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/dashboard:latest'
  container_name: dashboard
  restart: always
  ports:
    - '127.0.0.1:4200:80'
  networks:
    - rescale-net
  depends_on:
    - state-manager
  labels:
    io.portainer.accesscontrol.teams: rescale-all

krakend:
  image: 'harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/krakend:latest'
  container_name: krakend
  ports:
    - '127.0.0.1:3005:8080'
  networks:
    - rescale-net
  labels:
    io.portainer.accesscontrol.teams: rescale-all

networks:
  rescale-net:
    name: rescale-net
```

Listing 11: Docker Compose configuration for RESCALE development deployment.

6.2 TBOM creation: end-to-end flow

This appendix provides a complete representation of the TBOM creation flow, covering all interactions between the involved components. This flow is a direct reference to the processes described in Section 3.3 Supported Flows, where each step has been detailed in terms of its functional and technical role within the Trust Orchestrator Framework.

Below, we provide both:

1. A textual representation of the sequence diagram.
2. The generated sequence diagram itself for better visualization.

If the reader wishes to recreate or modify the diagram, the textual description can be copied and pasted into sequencediagram.org [21]. The tool will automatically generate the visual representation, making it easier to analyze and refine the flow.

Guidelines for Using sequencediagram.org

To generate the diagram:

1. Copy the provided text below.
2. Go to sequencediagram.org.
3. Paste the text into the editor.
4. Download or export the diagram (optional)

This approach ensures that the TBOM creation process remains traceable, editable, and reproducible, allowing easy updates and refinements as needed.

```
title TBOM creation flow
database "Code Repositories" as code
actor "producer" as user
actor "consumer" as user2
participant "Dashboard" as dash
participant "Auth" as auth
participant "Harbor" as harbor
participant "SSCG Generator" as sscg
participant "DSCG Generator" as dscg
participant "State Manager" as SM
participant "TrustOR" as trustor
database "Repositories" as repos
participant "Security Assurance" as seca
participant "Block-chain" as bc
```

```
# login part
```

```
user->dash:login
```

```
dash->auth:check credentials
```

```
dash<-auth: OK
```

```
user<-dash: success
```

```
# register component / receive UUID
```

```
user->dash:register SW or HW component
```

```
dash->SM:setComponent(●Name, Programming Language\netc...)
```

```
SM->auth:Validate Auth Token
```

```
auth->SM: Success
```

```
note over SM:Extract userID from Auth Token\nCalculate Component Hash  
(●Name + userID)\nAdd userID to Component\nAdd Hash to Component
```

```
SM->dash: Success
```

```
note over dash: ● Name\nProgramming Language\netc...
user<-dash:success
user->dash:get access token
dash->SM: get access token
SM->auth:Validate Auth Token
auth->SM: Success
note over SM:Generate Access Token 📄 \n(Hash + Auth Token)
SM->dash:return access token 📄
user<-dash:return access token 📄
```

```
# ----- Static Analysis -----
```

```
# download Static Analysis container
```

```
==Static Analysis==#fff7b9
```

```
user->harbor: request the Static Analysis container
```

```
user<-harbor: download the Docker image file
```

```
note over user:Execute Docker container\nwith the configuration\nparameters needed:\n📄 access token\n▶ dry-run false\n● SBOM:\n - ● name\n - 📄 version
```

```
code->user:pull component\n(version 📄)
```

```
note over user: run the Static Analysis
```

```
# run Static Analysis / submit result
```

```
user->sscg: Static Analysis results are all gathered
```

```
note over sscg:Result:\n● SBOM:\n - ● name\n - 📄 version\n● SSCG:\n - ● SBOM serialNumber\n - ● SBOM hash
```

```
sscg->SM: send result
```

note over SM:Pre-checks:\n📄 access token validation\nparse token to retrieve component's hash\n✔ check if component with this hash exists
sscg<--SM:if check failed, abort

note over SM:retrieve software version from 🟡 SBOM\nretrieve SSCG Serial Number from 🔴 SSCG\n

platform handles the result

SM->trustor: send 🟡 SBOM 🔴 SSCG

note over trustor:Pre-checks (1):\n✔ check (🟢 name:📄 version) exists

SM<--trustor:if check failed, abort

sscg<--SM:if check failed, abort

note over trustor:Pre-checks (2):\n✔ SSCG must reference correctly\nthe SBOM serialNumber

SM<--trustor:if check failed, abort

sscg<--SM:if check failed, abort

note over trustor:Pre-checks (3):\n✔ 🟡 SBOM unique serialNumber\n✔ 🔴 SSCG unique serialNumber

trustor->repos: check 🟡 SBOM unique serialNumber

trustor<-repos: response

SM<--trustor:if check failed, abort

sscg<--SM:if check failed, abort

trustor->repos: check 🔴 SSCG unique serialNumber

trustor<-repos: response

SM<--trustor:if check failed, abort

sscg<--SM:if check failed, abort

note over trustor:Pre-checks (4):\n✔ 🟡 SBOM is valid CycloneDX\n✔ 🔴 SSCG is valid CycloneDX\n✔ auth and integrity of SSCG

SM<--trustor:if check failed, abort

```
sscg<--SM:if check failed, abort
```

```
note over trustor:hash the ● SBOM and store it
```

```
trustor->repos: save SBOM
```

```
note over repos: ● SBOM
```

```
trustor<-repos: success
```

```
trustor->repos: save SSCG
```

```
note over repos: ● SSCG\n✓ includes ● SBOM serialNumber\n✓ includes ● SBOM hash
```

```
trustor<-repos: success
```

```
SM<-trustor:success
```

```
note over SM:Update Component Version with: \n - ● SBOM version\n - ● SSCG Serial Number
```

```
sscg<-SM: success
```

```
user<-sscg:success
```

```
# ----- Dynamic Testing -----
```

```
==Dynamic Testing==#fff7b9
```

```
# login part
```

```
user2->dash:login
```

```
dash->auth:check credentials
```

```
dash<-auth: OK
```

```
user2<-dash: success
```

```
alt manual SSCG selection through Dashboard
```

```
user2->dash:browse for component\n(filter search with ● name: 12 version)
```

```
user2<-dash:the public part of ● SSCG
```

else get SSCG using API

user2->SM:get SSCG (parameters: ● name, 1234 version)

user2<-SM:the public part of ● SSCG

end

user2->dash:get access token

user2<-dash:receive access token 📄

download Dynamic Testing container

user2->harbor: request the Dynamic Testing container

user2<-harbor: download the Docker image file

note over user2:Execute Docker container\nwith the configuration\nparameters needed:\n📄 access token\n▶ dry-run false\n● SSCG serialNumber

code->user2:pull artifact\n(vesrion 1234)

note over user2: run the Dynamic Testing

run Dynamic Testing / submit result

user2->dscg: Dynamic Testing results are all gathered

note over dscg:Result:\n● DSCG with:\n● SSCG serialNumber

dscg->SM: send result

note over SM:Pre-checks:\n📄 access token validation\nparse token to retrieve component's hash\n✓ check if component with this hash exists\n✓ check if ● SSCG serialNumber exists

sscg<--SM:if check failed, abort

note over SM:Use ● SSCG serialNumber to find\nthe version of the component\nretrieve DSCG Serial Number\nfrom ● DSCG

platform handles the result

SM->trustor: send DSCG

note over trustor:Pre-checks (1):\n✓ ● DSCG must reference an \nexisting ● SSCG serialNumber

trustor->repos: check ● SSCG serialNumber exists

trustor<-repos: response

SM<--trustor:if check failed, abort

sscg<--SM:if check failed, abort

note over trustor:Pre-checks (2):\n✓ ● DSCG unique serialNumber

trustor->repos: check ● DSCG unique serialNumber

trustor<-repos: response

SM<--trustor:if check failed, abort

sscg<--SM:if check failed, abort

note over trustor:Pre-checks (3):\n✓ ● DSCG is valid CycloneDX\n✓ auth and integrity of DSCG

SM<--trustor:if check failed, abort

sscg<--SM:if check failed, abort

trustor->repos: save DSCG

note over repos: ● DSCG with:\n - ● SSCG serialNumber

trustor<-repos: success

note over trustor:Generate a\n◆ TBOM_serialNumber

SM<-trustor:success + ◆ TBOM_serialNumber

note over SM:Update Component Version with: \n - ● DSCG Serial Number

sscg<-SM: success

user2<-sscg:success

==TBOM creation==#fff7b9

group step-1: gather data

trustor->repos:(SSCG referenced,
then\nsearch for SBOM referenced\n

trustor<-repos:success

note over trustor:Generate an\nempty BOV

trustor->repos: store BOV

trustor<-repos: success

note over trustor: SBOM
(ref)\n - BOV (ref)

trustor->repos:store TBOM

trustor<-repos:success

end

SM-->trustor: SM can poll for TBOM updates

SM<--trustor:

group step-2: add TBOM to Block-chain

trustor->bc:send TBOM

bc->bc:add TBOM\nto Block-chain

trustor<-bc:success + metadata

note over trustor: TBOM (metadata):\n - Hash\n - Transaction Index

trustor->repos:store TBOM metadata

trustor<-repos:success

end

SM-->trustor: SM can poll for TBOM updates

SM<--trustor:

group step-3: Communication with Security Assurance

trustor->seca:create a new project

trustor<-seca:receive project

trustor->trustor:create a new mapping:\n()

trustor->seca:submit the

trustor<-seca:success

end

SM<-trustor: TBOM step-3_completed notification

group step-4: BOV updates

trustor<-seca: updated

trustor->trustor:find the

trustor->repos: update

trustor<-repos: success

trustor->repos:update TBOM metadata

trustor<-repos:success

trustor->bc: UPDATE_BOV()

bc->bc:

trustor<-bc:success

SM<-trustor: BOV-update notification

end

TBOM creation flow

Static Analysis

Dynamic Testing

TBOM creation

